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RIGOUROUS -
secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

Deliverable 5.2

PLATFORM PROTOTYPE INTEGRATION AND IN-LAB TESTING 2

Title	Platform Prototype Integration and In-lab testing 2
Document description	This deliverable reports the work done for T5.1 and T5.2 of WP5, on the progress done for the integration and testing for the different platform assets, while showing their corresponding functionalities within lab environment.
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
AdvB	Advisory board
AP	Associated partner
BEN	Beneficiary
COO	Coordinator
DM	Dissemination Manager
DoA	Description of the action
EBOS	EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED
EC	European Commission
FCP	Focal Contact Point
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT-FI	ICTFICIAL OY
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ITAV	INSTITUTO DE TELECOMUNICACOES
LNVO	LENOVO DEUTSCHLAND GMBH
ONE	ONE SOURCE CONSULTORIA INFORMATICA LDA
ORO	ORANGE ROMANIA SA
OULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
PC	Project Coordinator
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PO	European Commission Project Officer
PU	Public
Starion	Starion LUXEMBOURG SA

UMU	UNIVERSIDAD DE MURCIA
UWS	UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND
WINGS	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE
WP	Work package
REST	Representational State Transfer
B5G	Beyond 5G
RBAC	Role based access control
NFC	Near Field communication
EPC	Evolved packet core
USRP	Universal software radio peripheral
NB-IoT	Narrow band internet of things
LTE-M	LTE-machines
LoRa	Long range
MEC	Mobile edge computing

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents Deliverable D5.2, Platform Prototype Integration and In-Lab Testing 2, as part of the RIGOUROUS project. Building on the foundational work of Deliverable D5.1 [1], which introduced the initial integration of the RIGOUROUS toolkit assets, D5.2 focuses on integrating, testing, and validating a cohesive prototype (Prototype 1) within a controlled laboratory environment. It captures the collaborative efforts of project partners in developing and testing the prototype while demonstrating its functionality under diverse cybersecurity threat scenarios.

The deliverable provides the integration details of key RIGOUROUS framework components, leveraging multiple testbeds to enable seamless communication and operation across various assets. The prototype integrates a subset of toolkit assets, concentrating on anomaly detection, trust evaluation, and mitigation enforcement in a simulated 5G/6G ecosystem. Significant progress is reported in implementing the Holistic Security and Privacy Framework, advanced anomaly detection systems, and AI-driven security orchestration modules. These assets have been successfully deployed and tested using UMU, OULOU, UWS, and ONE testbeds, which simulate real-world environments to ensure practical applicability.

Extensive in-lab testing forms a cornerstone of this deliverable, encompassing six distinct test cases and eight defined cyberattack scenarios, such as Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS), Denial-of-Service (DoS), IoT swarm attacks, and HTTP-based attacks. The integrated assets' performance was evaluated against these threats, with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used to measure accuracy, anomaly detection, and mitigation response times. The tests demonstrated the RIGOUROUS framework's capacity to effectively detect and mitigate cybersecurity threats, improving mitigation time and decision-making over existing state-of-the-art solutions.

This deliverable marks a significant milestone by validating the integration strategy and operational readiness of the RIGOUROUS framework's components. It also provides critical insights and feedback to refine and enhance the second prototype (Prototype 2), which will integrate the full toolkit and finalise the platform's capabilities. The results documented in D5.2 lay a strong foundation for the upcoming deliverable, D5.3, focusing on real-world use case demonstrations and comprehensive evaluations. By progressing through these carefully phased iterations, the RIGOUROUS project ensures its innovative cybersecurity solutions are robust, reliable, and ready to meet the demands of next-generation 5G/6G networks.

1 INTRODUCTION

This document marks the completion of Milestone 6, “In-Lab RIGOUROUS Integrated Framework Assessment, validated through the integration of Prototype 1 assets.” These assets span nearly all layers of the RIGOUROUS architecture and play a pivotal role in verifying that each component performs as expected, delivering accurate results and relevant information to adjacent assets or end users. This verification is achieved through in-lab testing, which ensures that integrated assets function seamlessly and smoothly within the RIGOUROUS framework.

Test cases are conducted in a controlled lab environment to confirm that interactions between assets and infrastructures occur without disruptions or inconsistencies. This phase allows for the early detection and resolution of potential integration challenges, ensuring that all components work harmoniously and contribute effectively to the system's overall performance. In-lab testing provides a vital validation layer before real-world deployment, reducing the risk of unforeseen issues and ensuring robustness across diverse operational scenarios.

Project partners have prepared a structured set of attack scenarios and storylines to assess these integrations thoroughly. These will demonstrate the response capabilities of the integrated assets and confirm the toolkit’s adaptability to various real-world conditions. The insights gained from this work will serve as a foundation for the upcoming tasks in T5.3, "Use Cases Showcasing, Validation, and Evaluation" [2], further highlighting the RIGOUROUS toolkit’s readiness and effectiveness in diverse operational contexts.

1.1. Document Structure

The structure of this document is organised as follows:

- **Section 1:** shows the introduction to the current deliverable.
- **Section 2:** explains the methodology and processes adopted for integrating the RIGOUROUS toolkit components. This section includes a breakdown of the two main integration milestones: the Preliminary Integrated Prototype (Prototype 1) and the Final Integrated Prototype (Prototype 2). Each prototype is described in terms of its purpose, timeline, and expected outcomes.
- **Section 3:** focuses on the technical aspects of Prototype 1, including its components and the testbeds used for its implementation. It begins with a Prototype Description that explains the overall architecture and objectives of Prototype 1. The Assets Involved in Prototype 1 subsection details the tools and modules that form the backbone of the prototype. This is followed by a detailed Description of Testbeds Used, covering the environments where the prototype was deployed. Further subsections delve into the “Integration of Anomaly Detectors to the 5G Core”, providing technical explanations of how specific anomaly detection frameworks are incorporated and “Mitigation Enforcement on the Telecommunications Network”, which describes the application of mitigation actions through AI-driven orchestration.

- **Section 4:** evaluates the functionality of Prototype 1 through various test cases designed to simulate different attack scenarios. This section begins with an “Attacks List”, which catalogues the potential threats addressed during testing. The Attack Template provides a standardised format for documenting these attack scenarios. Lastly, the “Test Cases” subsection describes in detail the execution and results of each test case, demonstrating the prototype’s ability to detect and mitigate attacks while meeting specific KPIs.
- **Section 5:** shows the conclusion of the current deliverable.

This comprehensive structure ensures a clear and logical presentation, guiding the reader from the initial integration plan to the final validation of Prototype 1.

2 INTEGRATION PLAN

This section summarises and updates the integration plan previously presented in deliverable D5.1. The primary objective of RIGOUROUS integration is to achieve a unified prototype of the RIGOUROUS framework, building upon the architecture and components developed within the scope of Work Packages 2, 3 and 4. Previously, deliverable D5.1 reported on the “Initial version of application enablers and software modules” (MS5). The present deliverable, D5.2, reports the ongoing work towards the second and final functional prototype, aiming to achieve the “Final RIGOUROUS enablers and framework” (MS7).

This section is organised as follows:

- Methodology (Section 2.1): updates the integration methodology.
- Integration Overview (Section 2.2): describes the interface definition between components.
- Roadmap (Section 2.3): presents the roadmap of both the preliminary integrated prototype and the final integrated prototype.

2.1. Methodology

The integration methodology, illustrated in Figure 1, as defined in Section 2 of D5.1 involves several steps to integrate RIGOUROUS framework assets. This deliverable, D5.2, represents a midpoint of the second prototype integration (to be completed by M30) and the preliminary In-Lab Testing results on the integrated prototype (to be completed by M34), detailed in Section 4.

Figure 1: Integration Methodology.

2.2. Integration Overview

The integration plan includes defining an interface template for RIGOROUS assets. Previous deliverable D5.1 defined a standard template, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Interfaces template.

Field	Description
Interface Code	Unique identifier of the interface
Status	design development testing validation completed
Component #1	Component name
Component #2	Component name
Direction	#1 to #2 #2 to #1
Description	A short description of the interface
Mode	Synchronous/Asynchronous
Standard/Protocols	e.g., REST, UDP, TCP, HTTP, RPC, etc
Format	e.g., JSON, YAML, XML, etc
Endpoint	e.g., API/endpoint
Operation	e.g., GET, POST, publish, subscribe
Request/Data Schema	Schema of the request/data
Request/Data Example	Example request/data
Response Schema	Schema of the response (optional)
Response Example	Example response data (optional)
Impact on #Component 1	A short description of the impact on #Component 1 (optional)
Impact on #Component 2	A short description of the impact on #Component 2 (optional)

Several interfaces were defined based on this template. Their complete definitions can be found in ANNEX A—Interface Definition. A summary of the integration interfaces is presented in Table 2 below. This table outlines the interfaces used in the current preliminary prototype, those expected to be included in the final prototype, and the status of each.

Table 2: Integration Interfaces.

#	Interface abbreviation	Component #1	Partner #1	Component #2	Partner #2	Development Status
1	OT-PUI	Onboarding Tools (OT)	ITAV	Human Controllable Privacy UI (PUI)	ITAV	Development
2	OT-AOUI	Onboarding Tools (OT)	ITAV	Application Onboarding UI (AOUI)	ITAV	Development

3	OT-SCUI	Onboarding Tools (OT)	ITAV	Service Composition UI (SCUI)	ITAV	Development
4	OT-WEB_UI	Onboarding Tools (OT)	ITAV	Enhanced Human Centric VNF Catalog Management UI (WEB_UI)	ITAV	Development
5	OT-SO	Onboarding Tools (OT)	ITAV	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Development
6	OT-TRA	Onboarding Tools (OT)	ITAV	Threat Risk Assessor (TRA)	Starion	Development
7	OT-PQ	Onboarding Tools (OT)	ITAV	Privacy Quantifier (PQ)	ITAV	Development
8	SO-ISM	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Intent-Based Security Manager (ISM)	UMU	Development
9	SO-NFV_MANO	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	(NFV_MANO)	UMU	Development
10	SO-SA	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Security Agent (SA)	UMU	Development
11	SO-TESF	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification (TESF)	LNVO	Development
12	SO-SM	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Slice Manager (SM)	UWS	Validation
13	TESF-AID	Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification (TESF)	LNVO	AI-driven decision making (AID)	EBOS	Development
14	SM-NSP	Slice Manager (SM)	UWS	Network Self Protection (NSP)	UWS	Validation
15	HSPF-MTD	R12 [ONE] Holistic Security and Privacy Framework (HSPF)	ONE	MTD-based Robust ML Models (MTD)	OULU	Development
16	PPFLAD-EaaS	R12 [OULU] Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	OULU	Encryption as a Service (EaaS)	ICT-FI	Development
17	AID-PPFLAD	AI-driven decision making (AID)	EBOS	R12 [OULU] Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	OULU	Validation
18	AID-PPFAIAD	AI-driven decision making (AID)	EBOS	R12 [UMU] Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection	UMU	Development
19	AID-HSPF	AI-driven decision making (AID)	EBOS	R12 [ONE] Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	Validation
20	AID-CPC	AI-driven decision making (AID)	EBOS	Cyber-Physical Correlator (CPC)	WINGS	Development
21	AID-TRA	AI-driven decision making (AID)	EBOS	Threat Risk Assessor (TRA)	Starion	Validation
22	NSFM-SMPS	Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM)	UWS	Service Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS)	UWS	Validation

23	SMPS-SO	Service Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS)	UWS	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Validation
24	TIA-SMPS	Topology Inventory Agent (TIA)	UWS	Service Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS)	UWS	Validation
25	TIA-SM	Topology Inventory Agent (TIA)	UWS	Slice Manager (SM)	UWS	Validation
26	EDoS_DM	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator (EDoS_M)	OULU	Data Monitoring (DM)	Testbed Owners	Validation
27	EDoS_M-AC	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator (EDoS_M)	OULU	Admission Controller (AC)	OULU	Development
28	NMTD-SO	Network-based MTD modeling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management (NMTD)	ITAV	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Development
29	NMTD-TRA	Network-based MTD modeling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management (NMTD)	ITAV	Threat Risk Assessor	TRA	Development
30	AID-SO	AI-Driven Decision Making (AID)	EBOS	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Validation
31	PPFLAD-MS	R12 [OULU] Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	OULU	Monitoring System (MS)	OULU	Validation
32	PEAgent-SO	Policy Enforcement Agent (PEAgent)	OULU	Security Orchestrator (SO)	UMU	Validation

2.3. Roadmap Overview

2.3.1. Preliminary Integrated Prototype (Prototype 1)

As outlined in the executive summary of this document, Prototype 1 is composed of the RIGOROUS assets integrated initially at the time of EuCNC 2024, later revisited and improved. This marked the beginning of the corresponding in-lab testing phase, which commenced in M18 of the project plan. As illustrated in Figure 2, this phase spans until M24 and serves as a feedback loop for the second phase, focusing on Prototype 2.

The key milestones and steps related to Prototype 1 during this phase are as follows:

- M18: Readiness of the assets comprising Prototype 1

- All RIGOUROUS assets making up Prototype 1 were developed and prepared for integration.
- M20: Definition of all feasible attacks
 - All planned attacks to be showcased during this phase were defined, and the necessary tools and instruments were prepared for testing.
- M22: Definition of test cases and storylines
 - Six distinct test cases were identified in collaboration with all partners involved in Prototype 1, and the corresponding storylines were generated and prepared for execution.
- M23: Actual testing
 - Multiple configuration adjustments and fine-tuning rounds were carried out among the partners to conduct the six test cases. The results met the expected outcomes and aligned with the maturity level of the assets at this stage.

2.3.2. Final Integrated Prototype (Prototype 2)

Figure 2 presents a high-level roadmap for the second (and final) integrated prototype. This roadmap extends the one previously presented in D5.1, providing additional detail on the relevant phases to complete Prototype 2 by M30.

Figure 2: Second Prototype Roadmap.

The key steps for the successful achievement of the second (and final) prototype are the following:

- M25: Mature state of all Assets
 - All RIGOUROUS Assets will achieve a mature state by M25, allowing the start the second prototype integration by M26.

- M26: Start of Second Prototype Integration
 - The second prototype integration activities will start at M26, aiming to validate the correct behaviour of the entire RIGOUROUS framework.
- M28: Threat Scenarios Validation
 - The UCs threat scenarios, initially defined in D2.2, will be tested by M28.
- M29: Cross-Layer Validation
 - The previous step will identify any missed configurations or improvements needed, which will be promptly addressed. Then, by M29, new validation activities will be conducted to ensure the correct behaviour of the RIGOUROUS framework, now improved by the feedback from the activities conducted with the RIGOUROUS UCs.
- M30: Second Prototype

The second (and final) prototype will be achieved by M30, along with the submission of D5.3.

3 PRELIMINARY INTEGRATED PROTOTYPE

3.1. Prototype description

The integration follows the RIGOUROUS architecture, mapping assets to specific functional blocks. In the first phase, a preliminary prototype (Prototype 1) was developed to integrate and test a subset of assets from the RIGOUROUS architecture. This prototype facilitates an initial architecture validation, providing valuable results to the technical work packages (3 and 4) for potential improvements. Subsequently, MS7 will finalise the RIGOUROUS enablers and frameworks outlined in deliverable D5.3. Figure 3 depicts the assets in the current testing activities and presents the primary interactions.

The integration of prototype 1 leverages multiple testbeds to accommodate multiple deployment domains. To ensure inter-asset communication across different testbeds, a Kafka instance was deployed within the OneSource testbed and made accessible to all partners. Several Kafka topics were established to facilitate this communication.

Overall, Prototype 1 aims to demonstrate the seamless and successful integration of the RIGOUROUS toolkit's modules. This is achieved through the execution of six carefully designed test cases, which are detailed in Section 4. These test cases focus on simulating different attack scenarios, as outlined in Section 4.1, to evaluate the behaviour and performance of the involved assets under various threat conditions. By conducting these tests, Prototype 1 provides a solid foundation for assessing the operational flow, interoperability, and resilience of the RIGOUROUS toolkit components in addressing cybersecurity challenges.

Section 3.2 provides detailed information about assets included in the preliminary prototype testing activities, including the specific testbed used and deployment details for each asset.

Figure 3: Mapping of preliminary prototype assets to the RIGOUROUS architecture.

3.2. Assets Involved in Prototype 1

For the prototype 1 environment setup, we have integrated a range of assets across multiple testbeds operated by different project partners. This setup will facilitate end-to-end testing of RIGOUROUS components and their interactions within a controlled environment, allowing us to validate each asset's performance and interoperability.

Each asset is deployed on a specific testbed, reflecting the partner's role and the infrastructure requirements. Table 3 shows the different assets involved and the type of interfaces.

Table 3: Prototype 1 assets.

Asset	Partner	Testbed	Interface Type	Interaction
R02 - Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification	UMU	UMU, ONE	internal	R07
R03 - Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps	ITAV	ONE	KAFKA	R19
R04 - Onboarding tools	ITAV	ONE	REST API	R07
R07 - AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments	UMU	UMU, ONE	REST API	R11, R16
R08 - Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification	LNVO	UMU	KAFKA	R07, R16
R11 - Slice manager	UWS	UWS	R07: REST API R20: RABBITMQ	R07, R20
R11 - Network Self-Protection	UWS	UWS	RABBITMQ	R11, R20
R12 - Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	ONE	KAFKA	R16
R12 - Privacy-preserving Federated AI for anomaly detection	UMU	UMU	KAFKA	R16
R12 - Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	OULO	OULO	R16: KAFKA R07: REST API	R07, R16
R16 - AI-driven decision making	EBOS	EBOS	R12: KAFKA R19: KAFKA R07: REST API	R07, R12 and R19
R19 - Threat Risk assessor (TRA)	Starion	EBOS	KAFKA, REST	R16
R20 - SOAR solution: Resource Inventory Agent, Security Detection Tool, Security Planner	UWS	UWS	REST, RABBITMQ	R07, R11
R21 - Encryption as a Service	ICTFI	ONE (K8s)	HTTP or REST API	R12 (OULO)

Figure 4 shows the main communication links between the different assets.

Figure 4: Prototype 1 communication links.

Figure 4 presents the environment setup involving diverse testbeds and interfaces such as KAFKA, REST, and RABBITMQ, ensuring each asset functions cohesively within the more extensive RIGOROUS architecture. Figure 5 below shows the actual logical architecture used, showing where each component is deployed and the different interconnections each has.

Figure 5: Actual logical architecture of prototype 1.

3.3. Description of Testbeds Used

In prototype 1, 3 testbeds are involved where the different assets are deployed.

3.3.1. ONE Testbed

OneSource’s testbed, shown in Figure 6, is a cutting-edge, versatile environment designed to support developing, testing, and validating advanced solutions, leveraging cloud-native and virtualised technologies for B5G/6G paradigms. It comprises a cloud-based infrastructure with a 3-node Proxmox hypervisor hosting a robust 3-node Kubernetes cluster dedicated to R&D activities at OneSource premises. RIGOUROUS partners are provided with isolated environments to validate their assets. These clusters have advanced features, such as persistent volume claims, load balancers and ingress controllers. Additionally, the testbed offers technologies like OpenStack and Rancher, enabling the on-demand creation of resources (e.g., Kubernetes Clusters, VMs, etc.) to support diverse activities requiring dynamic environments.

Proxmox leverages Ceph as a storage solution, complemented by a dedicated Network File System (NFS) storage unit for the Kubernetes cluster. The testbed is crucial for facilitating the testing and evaluating the RIGOUROUS framework assets and supporting integration and showcasing activities. RIGOUROUS partners can access the testbed via a secure VPN connection.

Figure 6: OneSource testbed components.

Generic Information: Table 4 to Table 7 below show the main characteristics and the innovations of the testbed, along with mapping with RIGOUROUS KPIs/KVIs.

Table 4: Generic Information.

Generic Information	
Testbed number	4
Testbed name	ONE

Testbed location	Coimbra, Portugal
Responsible partner	ONE
Testbed with 5G	No
Cloud Infrastructure without 5G	Yes
Provides remote access	Yes
Provides a Kubernetes environment	Yes
Will it be integrated with the RIGOUROUS framework?	Yes

Table 5: Network Characteristics.

Topic
5G coverage
Complementary information about 5G Infrastructure
Complementary information about support Infrastructure (i.e., Kubernetes, others)
Remote Access

Table 6: Main Innovations.

Description	
Innovation name	Multi-node Kubernetes cluster
Innovation description	ONE provides a multi-node cluster with dedicated storage for developing, testing, and validating the different RIGOUROUS components and/or integrations between Assets and UCs.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a Kubernetes environment • Apply RBAC guidelines
Goals	Enable the validation of different RIGOUROUS components and integrations.

Table 7: Mapping with RIGOUROUS KPIs/KVIs.

Project KPI/KVI	Description
KPI-24	ONE testbed will be available for all the integrations required by the project. Remote access is provided, and set-up meetings are scheduled as needed to mitigate any issues with remote access and/or deployment.
KPI-29	ONE will support the deployment of different UCs (at least one), thus contributing to the testing and validation of the RIGOUROUS UCs.

3.3.2. UMU Testbed

The UMU testbed is supported by the Gaia lab in the Computer Science Faculty at the University of Murcia. The lab has a cloud platform hosting core network components and SDN, NFV and MEC deployments. Two OpenStack are deployed: rocky, a full-fledged deployment offering 160 vCPUs (Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6138 CPU based) and 512 GB RAM split into two compute nodes, one on each side and queens, a lightweight deployment offering 12 x86_64 vCPUs (Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2603 v3) based with 48 GB RAM and some ARM RPI 4 nodes with 4 vCPUs each (Broadcom BCM2711B0 quad-core A72 based) and 8GB RAM each. 5G SA network access is done using SDR technology; in particular, a few ETTUS B210 and ETTUS N310 are available for experimentation with other SDR options, such as BladeSDR boards. These SDR devices are accompanied by an 8 Core computer with 16GB RAM, the B210s, and a 16 Core (AMD EPYC 7302P based) with 32GB RAM server, the N310.

Besides, a commercial core has been acquired from Amarisoft with the associated RAN hardware, and both systems are fully integrated to have a completely functional and multi-site 5G solution. The deployment consists of two sites located at the Campus of Espinardo of the University of Murcia, and two cores are available: one turnkey solution by Amarisoft and an experimental one that can implement multiple open source 5G cores. The Amarisoft campus network is complemented by Callbox and Simbox units for complete in-lab experimentation. [FIGURE 7](#) shows the diagram of the general MEC services that the lab provides for the testbed.

Figure 7: UMU testbed.

3.3.3. OULOU Testbed

3.3.3.1. 5GTN Testbed

The University of Oulu has a 5G Test Network (5GTN) with a campus-wide small cell, macro-cell, and distributed antenna-based cellular network, which will be complemented by an NFV-based EPC and 5G backhauling solution [3]. Figure 8 provides a comprehensive overview of the platform’s architecture.

A full-scale 5G test network supports using 5G devices, higher frequency bands, cognitive management functionalities, and system testing tools for new solutions. The 5G Test Network feature evolution follows 5G research and standardisation progress, acting as a verification platform for theoretical 5G research. The network's cellular devices comprise 30 LTE small cells (700 MHz, 2.1, 2.3, 2.6, 3.5 GHz) and 2 macro cells (2.3 GHz). The network has two 5G NR base stations (3.5 GHz) complemented with User Equipment from MediaTek (10) that are easily integrated into any device and 5G-enabled mobile phones from several vendors. The network is supplemented by mmWave (24-28 GHz) 5G NR base stations and 36 remote radio head (RRH) based cloud RAN 5G NR devices. There are also pre-standard 5G capable NOKIA proof-of-concept (PoC) devices at 26-28 GHz for research. In Early 2023, the NOKIA Open edge system will be deployed, allowing the use of RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) with xApps.

Open air interface (OAI) 4G and 5G NR protocol stacks with USRP radios are also supported. The network is controlled by operator-grade EPC (Evolved Packet Core), thus making OULU a network operator with its own SIM production for mobile devices. The current operational EPC version is 5G NSA compliant, but a 5G standalone (SA) core is also available for research purposes. The network within the campus is complemented by a wireless sensor network (IoT, Internet of Things) extension with an estimated 2,000 different kinds of sensors with wireless connectivity through NB-IoT, LTE-M, and LoRa. Furthermore, the network has big data computing servers for data analytics. Some servers are distributed within the network, thus allowing MEC and caching services. The NOKIA EPC has open application programming interfaces (virtualised EPC) that enable the integration of new services, e.g., network management.

Figure 8: OULU's 5GTN Testbed.

It is worth mentioning that although 5GTN is dedicated to research, its management is still under the exclusive control of its equipment vendor. OULU will do its best to facilitate its usage for project demonstrations if needed.

3.3.3.2. 5G Testbed

For development, testing, and demonstration purposes in 6G SNS projects involving OULU, particularly RIGOROUS and 6G-SANDBOX, the cPouta cloud computing service of the Finnish National IT Centre for Science (CSC) [4] is leveraged. cPouta is a self-administered OpenStack-based Infrastructure-as-a-Service platform offering high-performance computing with superior flexibility and user experience. The cPouta virtual machines (VMs) are connected to the high-performance Funet network (Finnish University and Research Network), a backbone network providing Internet connections for Finnish higher education institutions and other research facilities.

As illustrated in Figure 9, we built a 5G testbed based on a Kubernetes (K8s) cluster set up on OULU’s cPouta platform. Open5GS [4] and UERAN-SIM [5] are used to implement the 5G SA Core and simulate the 5G RAN and User Equipment (UEs), respectively. The K8s cluster provides a monitoring system based on Prometheus. Furthermore, it offers an advanced autoscaling service that uses the K8s built-in Horizontal Pod Autoscaling (HPA) functionality, which we extended with the event-driven scale feature provided by the open-source KEDA tool.

In addition, several VMs with different flavours have been created and dedicated to the development and deployment of OULU’s assets as well as other partners’ assets. Some VMs serve as a platform for training and testing the ML models and creating the docker images. To this end, several open-source tools have been installed on these VMs, including Keras, TensorFlow, Pytorch, Docker, FastAPI, Flask, and Python. The VMs can be accessed by external users through a keypair-based SSH connection.

Figure 9: OULU’s 5G Testbed on CSC Cloud.

3.4. Integration of Anomaly Detectors to the 5G Core

3.4.1. R12 - Holistic Security and Privacy Framework:

The Holistic Security Privacy Framework (HSPF), a FL-based anomaly detection framework tailored for cloud-native environments, has been designed and developed with a strong focus on data privacy and security.

To collect data from the Network, the HSPF Collector is used. The latter implements a custom plugin associated with the NFStream [1] packet extraction library. The collected data is represented using the CIC-IDS2017 [2] feature vector. The data is then shared with the HSPF Agent, using a temporary shared storage.

On its hand, the HSPF Agent provides network inference over the collected traffic and continuous FL-based ML training. Additional details on the architecture, data monitoring and validation of the HSPF framework can be found in Section 6.4 of D4.2.

3.4.2. R12 - Privacy-preserving Federated AI for anomaly detection

To integrate UMU's R12 asset within the network, six different modules were used:

1. **5G Monitoring Sensor:** this module monitors in real-time a certain network interface, analyzing each received packet and creating a JSON summary with the relevant values for anomaly detection, i.e., important fields from each layer to calculate flow features. Each packet summary is published to a topic enabled for this purpose in a Kafka broker.
2. **5G Flow Processor:** this module receives in real-time the packet summaries from the previous module by active listening the Kafka topic. The packet information is aggregated and several flows based on packets' IPs and ports are created and statistics for each one is calculated. These statistics are published again to a different Kafka topic for the next module to consume them.
3. **Federated Learning Agent:** in training phase, it will receive in real-time the flow features from the previous module, until a certain threshold (configurable when the module is started) is reached. Once this condition is met, it registers against an FL Aggregator, and the FL process will begin when enough agents start the training.
4. **Federated Learning Aggregator:** in training phase, it will coordinate the registered agents throughout the learning process. It will indicate the flow features which have to be used from the original set, which privacy-preserving mechanism must be applied to the exchanged model updates by the agents, etc.
5. **Anomaly Detection Engine:** in the inference/detection phase, first, it will receive the final anomaly detection model (after training) from one of the FL agents. Then, loading a predefined testing dataset, the model is tested to extract the performance metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score) and starts listening for incoming flows for evaluation. For this purpose, another topic different from the used for training is configured. Next, for

each received flow, it decodes it, preprocesses the data, and evaluates the flow against the anomaly detection model, i.e., the Deep Autoencoder. In case the error threshold is surpassed, the flow is targeted as anomalous, and it is directed to the next module for classification into one specific attack class. Finally, once the attack label is received, it creates the STIXv2 alert using all the required information and publishes it in the R12-AID-TRA topic so that the AID can consume the information and proceed with the loop.

6. **Attack Classification Engine:** in inference/detection phase, it will listen actively using a REST method for incoming flows (received from the Anomaly Detection Engine) to be classified into one of the known attack classes. Previously, the model used for classification (a multi-class classification DNN) has been trained in a centralized way from a predefined multiclass dataset containing samples for all known attacks. In case the confidence of the classification does not reach a certain threshold (configurable at start time), the flow is classified as “Unknown”, alerting that a possible zero-day attack may be happening. This functionality allows the asset to potentially detect these kinds of unknown attacks.

3.4.3. R12 - Privacy-preserving FL-based anomaly detector

This asset is deployed and tested in the OULU testbed. The 5G testbed deployed on the CSC cloud is used to validate the functionality of the asset’s modules and for performing in-lab testing.

In this first prototype, we built upon and evolved the anomaly detection asset developed in the 6G-SANDBOX [9] project, effectively showcasing the cross-collaboration between 6G SNS projects. We leveraged the monitoring system developed in 6G-SANDBOX to collect traffic from UPF and extract network flow features required for anomaly detection. However, we updated the anomaly detection module to support the unified data models defined in RIGOUROUS to facilitate interaction between the Security Analytics Engine (SAE) and the AI-driven Decision Engine (AID). More details on the unified data models defined in RIGOUROUS can be found in section 6.1 in deliverable D4.2 [3]. Furthermore, the communication model of the anomaly detector has been updated to use KAFKA to publish the anomaly reports to AID. Finally, a new module, called Policy Enforcement Agent (PEAgent), has been developed to enforce the security policy received from the Security Orchestrator. It is worth mentioning that this asset's development is made in a way that facilitates the integration of the privacy-preserving FL-based anomaly detection models we have developed in WP4 in the final prototype.

Figure 10 illustrates the main components of the asset. All components are packaged as docker images and deployed either as sidecars or services in K8s. The monitoring system consists of (i) a traffic capture probe deployed as a **tcpdump sidecar** to UPF, allowing continuous collection of network traffic from/to the monitored resource, and (ii) a **Collector**, deployed as K8s service, to extract network flow features. The **Detector**, deployed as a K8s service, incorporates the DL model for detecting anomalous network flows caused by HTTP-based application-layer DDoS attacks. Finally, the **PEAgent** is deployed as a sidecar to UPF, exposing an external service for interaction with SO. The Collector, Detector, and PEAgent are FastAPI applications.

Figure 10: Deployment of R012-OULU's components.

- The anomaly detection module (i.e., Detector)
 - exposes a FastAPI endpoint (**/mlp/predict/**) to interface with the Collector. This interface allows to post the extracted network flow features as a csv file, which the DL module will then analyse to discriminate anomalous network flows.
 - supports an event-driven communication mode, using a Kafka Broker, to interface with AID. For each anomalous network flow detected, an anomaly report in STIX2 format is published to R12-AID-TRA topic, to which AID is subscribed. The anomaly report is a STIX2's bundle following the unified data model defined in WP4.
- The Collector exposes a FastAPI endpoint (**/uploadfile/**) to interface with the tcpdump sidecar. This interface allows to post the network traffic collected in a pcap file, which will then be analysed to extract the network flow features in a CSV file.
- The PEAgent exposes two FastAPI endpoints (**/add-rule/** and **/delete-rule/**) to add (using the HTTP POST method) or delete (using the HTTP DELETE method) a DROP FORWARD rule to/from the UPF's iptables, respectively. The **/add-rule/** endpoint is used to interface with SO, allowing to block the source (i.e., UE) of a malicious network flow detected by the Detector.

As depicted in Figure 10, the anomaly detector is fully integrated with the monitoring system (i.e., Collector), the AID (R16) asset in EBOS testbed and the SO (R07) in UMU testbed, providing a fully automated AI-driven closed loop for detecting and mitigating HTTP-based application-layer DDoS attacks launched by UEs against a Video-on-Demand service. The integration with AID is performed through the Kafka broker deployed in ONE testbed.

3.4.4. R08–Trust Evaluation & Trust enabler service function

The TESH (Trust Enabler and Service Function) has been developed in a local environment on a VM environment and has been deployed in the UMU testbed in Murcia with SSH-based access to their servers. In the UMU testbed, for the simulation of the attack and response of the Trust Manager, an open-source 5G Core Network - Open5gs has been deployed along with UERANSIM for simulating the RAN and UEs. This result gives a functional test environment that represents a virtual 5G RAN and Core network integrated with the trust manager, a Decision Engine, and a Security Orchestrator.

The Trust Manager has been deployed as a Flask Server, while the monitoring agents Prometheus and Alert Manager have been deployed as services that gather data from the Open5gs Core based on predefined alerts and rules of potential violation. Furthermore, the network function logs, namely AMF and SMF, are fetched and analysed in real-time from the docker containers logs. The deployment can be represented as in Figure 11.

Figure 11: R08 deployment

The Trust Manager or the TESH has the channel of communication to notify the Decision engine regarding the trust posture of an entity in the network, within this communication channel the TESH will send the trust score, IP of a network entity and impacted IP to the Decision Engine in events where the trust score of a network is below a given threshold. This communication takes place through KAFKA. The integration process of the TESH has been done on the UMU testbed by deploying the Trust manager as a Flask server through a webhook connected to a manager and Prometheus server. The TESH is set to interact with the decision engine AID through a KAFKA topic TESH-AID on which it publishes alerts on STIX format based on the threshold of the trust value of a network entity, it is worth noting here that within the context of this test, the AID module used was a dummy and a simulated version.

3.5. Mitigation enforcement on the 5G Core

3.5.1. R07 - AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments

For 5G network management, the security orchestrator plays a key role, extending its capabilities beyond the core network. When alerted, the orchestrator assumes responsibility for configuring and deploying network functions such as the vFirewall. These functions can be strategically deployed in various parts of the network, including the UPF, the gNB and/or the core. This flexibility allows the orchestrator to effectively manage and protect traffic. This configuration is done based on the use of policies arrived at the security orchestrator, which are translated and applied in the corresponding enabler. In this case the necessary rules are applied in the vfirewall allowing or blocking traffic based on the alerts.

In addition, the orchestrator is not only reactive but can also proactively optimise network performance and security. It ensures efficient traffic management on critical interfaces such as N2 and N3, safeguarding communication between key network components while minimising latency and mitigating potential threats.

By leveraging its advanced management capabilities, the orchestrator contributes to a more adaptable, scalable and secure 5G network. Also, using the anomaly detection and alerting system together with the orchestrator integration enhances the network by enabling a reactive threat scenario.

4 PRELIMINARY INTEGRATED PROTOTYPE (PROTOTYPE 1) VALIDATION

Prototype 1 comprised of all the assets described in Section 3 was tested in the lab environment. Three testbeds were integrated and used to run the test cases in Table 9. In this section, we will describe the attacks generated and captured, along with the corresponding test cases.

4.1. Attacks list

Below are the attacks that will be detected throughout the different test cases described and implemented in Section 4.3:

1. DDoS attack:

This attack is designed to disrupt the EMQX-BROKER deployment by generating overwhelming traffic using the `mqtt-stresser` [11] tool. The attack originates from external virtual machines (VMs) and targets the broker deployment through an external attacker vector. It involves 1024 clients sending 100 messages each, with a timeout of 5 seconds. The attack will be executed in 5 repetitions, each separated by a 5-minute interval. The attack setup includes configuration instructions on the GitLab page and will be launched via the command line.

2. DoS Attack (Slowhttptest)

This Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack targets the NGINX deployment by exploiting slow HTTP connections using the `Slowhttptest` [12] tool. Originating from external VMs, the attack vector involves an external attacker sending malformed HTTP requests. The payload involves dynamic configurations, with 5 repetitions spaced 5 minutes apart. The attack is configured with parameters such as 1000 concurrent connections and GET requests, as specified in the instructions available online. Execution is performed via the command line.

3. DoS on Control Plane

This attack targets the network's control plane, specifically the AMFs and other network functions (NFs), through NAS signalling using the N1 interface. The attack originates from user equipment (UEs) and leverages a shell script for execution. The payload details and duration are dynamically configurable, with the attack setup instructions uploaded on GitHub. It can be customised within the shell script before launching via the command line.

4. IoT-Swarm DDoS

This Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attack leverages a swarm of infected IoT devices to overwhelm the multi-domain 5G/6G infrastructure and inter-domain servers. Tools like `Bonesi` [13] and a network emulator orchestrate the attack, originating from infected UEs. The attack payload can be configured dynamically by parameters such as packet size, rate, steps, and spoofed IPs. This automated attack is executed as an orchestrated swarm botnet DDoS, simulating a large-scale IoT-based threat.

12. High-rate HTTP-based DDoS (HULK)

Using tools like DoS-Tool [14] and Doser [15], this high-rate HTTP-based DDoS attack targets the vCDN providing Video-on-Demand (VoD) services. The attack originates from UEs, simulating an external attacker overwhelming the vCDN. The payload and configuration are dynamic, and the attack requires manual iteration for execution. It is launched via the command-line interface to simulate high-traffic scenarios.

13. Low-rate HTTP-based DDoS (Slowloris)

This low-rate HTTP-based DDoS attack leverages tools like Slowloris [16] and Goloris [17] to disrupt the vCDN's Video-on-Demand service by simultaneously keeping multiple HTTP connections open. The attack originates from UEs, simulating an external attacker using slow requests to consume server resources. The payload is dynamically configurable to vary parameters like connection timeout. The attack is manually executed via the command-line interface, simulating a stealthy low-rate attack.

14. TCP SYN DoS (hping3)

For this attack, a setup composed of one malicious UE and one victim server is deployed in the UMU Open5GS testbed. The tool hping3 [18] will be leveraged to launch several TCP SYN messages against the victim, attempting to cause a DoS by consuming server resources. This script is manually executed using a CLI and the corresponding parameters ("flood" to launch a flooding attack and "S" to specify that TCP SYN messages must be used).

15. HTTP Brute-force dictionary attack

For this attack, similarly to attack 14, a setup composed of one malicious UE and one victim server is deployed in the UMU Open5GS testbed. The open-source tool Brute-force HTTP [19] will be leveraged to launch several login attempts with the same user and try all the passwords in a lightweight Hydra password-cracking list. The attack aims to find the right combination of user and password to log into the system illegally. This script is manually executed using a CLI and the corresponding parameters ("U" to specify the user, and "p" to specify the path to the password cracking list previously downloaded).

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4.2. Attack Template

Below Table 8 shows the template used to collect the information for each of the attack that will be detected within prototype 1:

Table 8: Attack template.

#	Name	Owner	Anomaly detector	SO Instance	Tools	Source	Destination	Vector	Payload information	Duration	Repetitions	Config	Setup	Origin
1	DDoS	ONE	R12 (ONE)	ONE	mqtt-stresser	External source (e.g., VMs)	EMQX-BROKER deployment	External attacker	NA	Dynamic	5 repetitions 5 min a part	Instructions available at Gitlab page	Clients: 1024 Messages: 100 Timeout: 5s	Attack launch via CMD
2	DoS Slowhttp test	ONE	R12 (ONE)	ONE	Slowhttp test	External source (e.g., VMs)	NGINX deployment	External attacker	NA	Dynamic	5 repetitions 5 min a part	Instructions available	-c 1000 -H -g -o slowhttp -i 10 -r	Attack launch via CMD

												on the website	200 -t GET -x 24 -p 3 -u <url-website>	
3	DoS on Control Plane	LNVO	R08	UMU	Shell Script UEs	AMFs and other NFs	External attacker	NAS signalling through N1 interface	Dynamic	NA		to be uploaded in github	can be configured within the shell script	Attack launch via CMD
4	IoT-Swarm DDoS	UWS	R20	UMU	Bonesi and network emulator	Infected UEs	Multi-domain 5G/6G infrastructure and inter-domain server	External attacker	Dynamic	NA	Internal IoT-Swarm configuration	Can be configured varying packet size, rate, steps, spoofed IPs, etc.	Automated and orchestrated swarm-iot botnet ddos attack	
12	High-rate HTTP-based DDoS (Hulk)	OULU	R12 (OULU)	UMU	DoS-Tool, doser tools	UEs	vCDN providing Video-on-Demand Service	External attacker	Dynamic	N/A	Manual iteration	Launch via CLI	Launch via CLI	
13	Low-rate HTTP-based DDoS (Slowloris)	OULU	R12 (OULU)	UMU	slowloris, goloris tools	UEs	vCDN providing Video-on-Demand Service	External attacker	Dynamic	N/A	Manual iteration	Launch via CLI	Launch via CLI	

14	TCP SYN DoS (hping3)	UMU	R12 (UMU)	UMU	hping3	UEs	Victim service deployed in UMU's 5G testbed	External attacker	N/A	Dynamic	1 repetition (1 command launch)	Basic configuration of the command (--flood and -S to perform the attack using the TCP SYN flag)	Launch via CLI	Launch via CLI
15	HTTP Dictionary attack	UMU	R12 (UMU)	UMU	Open-source tool (https://github.com/dmkngh/BruteforceHTTP)	UEs	Victim service deployed in UMU's 5G testbed	External attacker	N/A	Dynamic	1 repetition (1 command launch)	Basic configuration of the command (-U specifying the static user "user", and -p to specify the path to the password dictionary). A lightweight	Launch via CLI	Launch via CLI

												<i>t Hydra password dictionary is used.</i>		
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	---	--	--

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4.3. Test Cases

Below Table 9 shows the template used to collect the information for each of the test cases included in the prototype 1.

Table 9: Test cases included in prototype 1.

Test case ID	Test case name	Involved assets	Attack #	Partners involved
1	Dos-EMQX-Broker	R4, R7, R12, R16 and R19	1	ITAV, ONE, EBOS, UMU and Starion
2	DoS-Slowhttptest-NGINX	R4, R7, R12, R16 and R19	2	ITAV, ONE, EBOS, UMU and Starion
3	IoT Swarm DDoS	R07, R11, R20	4	UWS, UMU
7	Control Plane DOS attack	R08, R16, R7	3	LNVO, UMU
8	HTTP-based DDoS Attacks	R12, R7, R16	12 and 13	OULU, UMU, EBOS, Starion (Starion)
9	DoS and dictionary attacks	R12, R07	14 and 15	UMU

4.3.1. Test Cases 1 and 2

4.3.1.1. Description

Test cases 1 and 2 evaluate the RIGOUROUS architecture’s capability to detect and mitigate a DDoS attack targeting the EMQX-BROKER (test case 1) or a Slowhttptest-based DoS attack on an NGINX server (test case 2). The monitoring tools deployed on the ONE’s infrastructure continuously observe network activity. When the DDoS attack is initiated using the MQTT-stressor tool, the Holistic Security and Privacy Framework (HSPF, R12) detects the attack and promptly reports it to the RIGOUROUS framework. In detail, it posts a STIX message to the KAFKA topic "R12-AID-TRA", reporting the anomaly. The TRA (R19) component then consumes this message, processes it, correlates it with additional data, such as topology and network characteristics, and generates a refined STIX message. This updated message is posted on the KAFKA topic "TRA-AID." The AID (Anomaly and Intrusion Detection) component consumes the updated STIX message, executes its internal algorithms, and generates a mitigation action. This action is communicated to R07 through a REST API interface. Finally, R07 enforces the mitigation action directly on the testbed to neutralise

the DDoS attack. Figure 12 below shows the topology of both test cases involving assets along with the sequence of the messages.

Figure 12: Topology of test cases 1 and 2.

4.3.1.2. KPIs

The KPIs that will be measured within this test case are listed in the following Table 10:

Table 10: List of KPIs for test case 1&2.

KPI #	Description
KPI-12	Reduction of false alarms by at least 30%
KPI-13	Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%
KPI-15	Ability to detect 2 unknown/unexpected scenarios and >4 types of anomalies
KPI-16	Number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10
KPI-20	Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA
KPI-21	Improve decision-making on threat mitigation by 45% compared to SOTA

4.3.1.3. Results

A brief description of the RIGOUROUS components involved and their behaviour in this test is presented next:

- (i) Onboarding Tools [R04] were used to instantiate the applications to protect (An MQTT broker and a NGINX Ingress);
- (ii) HSPF (anomaly detection framework) [R12] was used to monitor and identify the attacks;
- (iii) TRA [R19] was used to determine the threat risk score of the identified attacks;
- (iv) AID [R16] was used to determine the best action to mitigate the identified attacks;
- (v) SO [R07] was used to mitigate the attack, in close action with the HSPF policy enforcer.

Figure 13 depicts the Onboarding of the MQTT application via the Onboarding Tools, which can be selected and deployed from the RIGOUROUS service catalogue.

The screenshot shows the OpenSlice Services Marketplace interface. The top navigation bar includes 'openslice', 'Services Marketplace', 'Manage Services', 'Manage Entities', and 'Monitoring'. On the left, the 'Service Catalog Explorer' sidebar shows a 'Catalog' dropdown with 'RIGOUROUS Services' selected. The main content area features a welcome message: 'Welcome to the OpenSlice by ETSI Services Marketplace. Browse available services and sign in to order.' Below this, it states 'Service Specifications of RIGOUROUS Services category' and 'Services from the RIGOUROUS catalogue'. A search bar labeled 'Filter services...' is present. Two service cards are displayed: 'EMQX Broker' (Version: 0.1.0, RIGOUROUS Services, EMQX MQTT broker, Last updated at 8 Jan 2025, 11:28:50) and 'HTTPBin' (Version: 0.1.0, RIGOUROUS Services, HTTPBin Service, Last updated at 17 Jan 2025, 15:31:49). Both cards include a 'Preview' button.

Figure 13: The onboarded MQTT application (EMQX Broker) can be instantiated from the RIGOUROUS service catalogue.

Figure 14 presents a sample of the anomalies detected by the HSPF and reported to the RIGOUROUS framework. The content of the image illustrates the expected behaviour of the HSPF when a specific anomaly is detected and the respective format under which it is communicated to the RIGOUROUS framework via the Kafka broker. The message follows the unified data format agreed upon under WP4 activities, which relies on the standardized STIX2 format [20].

Below, Figure 16, Figure 17 & Figure 18 show AID's behaviour when receiving an anomaly from the anomaly detector (HSPF, in this test), as well as the threat scores received from the TRA.

First the Figure 16 shows the received STIX messages generated by the R12 (HSPF in this case).

```
2025-01-08 09:26:02,567 [INFO] Consumed message ID: bundle--209374a3-25ff-4baa-8791-914ae0e0a543 From ONE
2025-01-08 09:29:13,036 [INFO] Consumed message ID: bundle--317216da-92e5-4ae7-bbb3-f676dc53e9f3 From ONE
```

Figure 16: Test case 1&2 messages received by AID.

As shown in Figure 16 above the bundle messages were successfully consumed by the AID. The AID then selects the specific action to be sent to the SO. In case of the attacks from ONE's infrastructure. the specified action that was sent to the SO was a firewall action as mentioned in the below Figure 17.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd"
xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd msp1.xsd">
  <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9">
    <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration">
      <capability>
        <Name>Firewall</Name>
      </capability>
      <configurationRule>
        <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="FirewallRuleAction">
          <firewallActionType>DROP</firewallActionType>
        </configurationRuleAction>
        <configurationCondition xsi:type="FirewallConfigurationCondition">
          <isCNF>false</isCNF>
          <ruleParameters>
            <isCNF>false</isCNF>
            <destinationAddress>0.0.0.0</destinationAddress>
            <action>drop</action>
            <sourceAddress>192.168.0.0</sourceAddress>
            <name>ejempl0</name>
          </ruleParameters>
          <configurationCondition>
            <externalData xsi:type="Priority">
              <value>60000</value>
            </externalData>
            <Name>Rule0</Name>
            <isCNF>false</isCNF>
          </configurationRule>
          <Name>Conf0</Name>
        </configuration>
        <enablerCandidates>
          <enabler>firewall</enabler>
        </enablerCandidates>
      </ITResource>
    </ITResourceOrchestration>
```

Figure 17: Test Case 1&2 mitigation action sent to SO.

Relevant information about the attack such as the source and destination IP addresses were taken from the STIX messages received from the R12 and the corresponding firewall action (using MSPL) was sent to the SO as shown in the below Figure 18.

```
08-01-2025 09:29:16 - The Security Policy has been enforce successfully
08-01-2025 09:29:16 - 10.244.198.85 - - [08/Jan/2025 09:29:16] "POST /webhook HTTP/1.1" 200 -
08-01-2025 09:29:16 - The Security Policy has been enforce successfully
08-01-2025 09:29:16 - 10.244.198.73 - - [08/Jan/2025 09:29:16] "POST /webhook HTTP/1.1" 200 -
```

Figure 18: Test case 1&2 successful policy enforcement message.

- KPI-12 has been measured using the False Positive Rate (FPR) formula, illustrated in Equation 1.

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (1)$$

- KPI-13 has been collected using the Accuracy formula, illustrated in Equation 2.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

- KPI-15 and KPI-16, at this stage, have been identified considering the number of attacks conducted in each test. Prototype 2 will potentially include complex scenarios with multiple threats per test, thus, the methodology to collect this KPI will be revised by then.
- KPI-20 has been measured considering the interval between the reporting of the anomaly by the R12 (HSPF) and the respective decision by R16 (AID). This included the score produced by the R19 (TRA).
- KPI-21 has been measured on an E2E basis, considering the moment from when the anomaly was published until the mitigation policy was enforced. This period included not only the steps measured for KPI-20, but also the processing time of R07 and the enforcement of the policy in the network by the R12 Enforcer.

Table 11: Test Cases 1 and 2: Obtained results.

KPI #	Test 1	Test 2	
KPI	Measured Value	Measured Value	Target Value
KPI-12	FAR: 45%	FAR: 47%	>30%
KPI-13	Accuracy: 75%	Accuracy: 71%	>95%
KPI-15	Anomalies detected: 1	Anomalies detected: 0	>4
KPI-16	Attacks detected: 1	Attacks detected: 1	>10
KPI-20	Mitigation Reaction Time: ≈ 3.5s	Mitigation Reaction Time: ≈ 3.5s	<240 seconds
KPI-21	Decision making: ≈ 2.5s	Decision making: ≈ 2.5s	<60 seconds

The obtained results confirm the achievement of KPI-20 and KPI-21, whereas the remaining results lack yet some maturity to achieve the desired KPIs. The obtained results will serve as baseline for further testing and validation activities, namely in the scope of the second prototype.

4.3.2. Test Cases 3

4.3.2.1. Description

UWS provides a set of assets and software components to establish a security cognitive self-protection loop for mitigating DDoS attacks in 5G/6G networks. This loop integrates various components, handling tasks from attack detection to mitigation planning and execution. Integration with UMU-SO plays a key role by enabling orchestration.

The experiment setup includes:

- 1 infected UE sending legitimate and malicious traffic.
- 1 ISP with active Edge and Core segments.
- 1 DSP spanning Edge and Core segments.
- DDoS attack bandwidth: 250 Mbps (UDP).
- Legitimate traffic bandwidth: 90 Mbps.
- The following RIGOUROUS assets deployed in ORO infrastructure:
 - R07-Security Orchestrator (UMU-SO)
 - R11-Slice Manager (UWS-SM)
 - R20-Slice Mitigation Planner Service (UWS-SMPS)
- The following RIGOUROUS results deployed in UWS infrastructure:
 - R11-Network Self-Protection (UWS-NSP)
 - R20-SOAR: Network Security Flow Monitoring (UWS-NSFM), Topology Inventory Agent (UWS-TIA).

Figure 20: Achieved deployment scenario of the cyberattack and the self-protection loop.

The demonstration scenario proposed in this section involves two main stakeholders: an Infrastructure Service Provider (ISP) and two or more Digital Service Providers (DSPs). The ISP

provides physical infrastructure, networking, computing devices, and a set of control and management planes where the assets involved in this scenario are deployed. The DSPs, in turn, deliver digital 5G telecommunication services. The ISP ensures tenant isolation, enabling multi-tenancy capabilities that allow multiple DSPs to utilize the ISP's physical resources. In Figure 20, the grey-coloured boxes represent the IP, depicting the connection of 5G gNBs and transport segment devices (e.g., physical routers and switches).

The proposed attack and mitigation scenario begins with an infected UE device connected to the 5G/6G infrastructure. This UE device simultaneously sends legitimate traffic (up to 100 Mbps) to a server and launches a DDoS attack (250 Mbps) orchestrated by a botnet (see 1 in Figure 20). The UE connects to a 5G gNB, which routes the client's traffic to the ISP's Edge server (see 2 in Figure 20). This traffic is then redirected by the ISP's VNF to the specific DSP associated with the UE. Once processed by the DSP, the traffic is marked with a new VXLAN encapsulation at the ISP's Edge exit point, enabling multi-tenancy and allowing subsequent infrastructure elements to correctly route the traffic to the appropriate DSP. After leaving the ISP's Edge server, the traffic is routed through the Transport layer to the ISP's Core server (see 3 in Figure 20). At the Core, the VXLAN encapsulation ensures that the server can determine the correct DSP destination for the traffic, allowing it to flow to its destination (see 4 and 5 in Figure 20).

Meanwhile, the ISP's control and management layers operate continuously. The UWS-TIA asset reports topology information—such as devices, connections, interfaces, and technologies—to the management plane (see 6 in Figure 20). This information is transmitted via a message bus deployed in the UWS management plane and consumed by the UWS-SMPS.

The transport segment router mirrors all inbound and outbound traffic, which is routed to the UWS management layer. Here, the UWS-NSFM is deployed and continuously monitors the mirrored interface (see 7 in Figure 20). Upon detecting a malicious attack, the UWS-NSFM analyses the threat and reports a detailed alert to the message bus, including metadata about the malicious 5G flow.

The UWS-SMPS consumes this alert, triggering its predictive analytics capabilities. By correlating network flow and topology information, it identifies the End-to-End (E2E) path of the malicious flow detected by the UWS-NSFM (see 8 in Figure 20). For this scenario, the red dots in Figure 20 represent the E2E path within the ISP's premises, specifically in the EGRESS direction. This information is formatted as a set of mitigation plans and sent to the UMU-SO via a REST API.

The UMU-SO orchestrates the mitigation process by defining specific steps required to create network slices at designated mitigation points. These orchestrated, intent-based instructions are sent to the UWS-SM via a REST API, detailing the actions needed for enforcement in the data plane. The UWS-SM identifies the network agents deployed across the infrastructure and communicates the mitigation actions to them. These network agents, represented as UWS-NSP components, are distributed across the ISP's Edge and Core servers (see 9 in Figure 20).

The UWS-NSP enforces the mitigation actions, creating network slices at the designated mitigation points (marked by red dots in Figure 20) and binding the malicious flows to these slices. As a result, the attack is mitigated automatically. These network slices are governed by policies determined by

the UWS-SMPS based on the cyberattack analysis. In this case, the policy limits the malicious flow’s bandwidth to 1 Kbps.

4.3.2.2. KPIs

The KPIs that will be measured within this test case are listed in the following Table 12:

Table 12: Test case 3 KPIs.

KPI #	Description
KPI-09	Number of End-to-End network slices supported.
KPI-10	Number of concurrent devices supported in the cognitive network management.
KPI-20	Decrease mitigation time by 50% compared to SOTA
KPI-22	Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop.

4.3.2.3. Results

Figure 21 illustrates the UWS-SMPS extraction of the E2E path, correlating detected malicious flow information with network topology data. This identifies all interfaces and hosts where the 1 Kbps network slice is applied, specifying whether the slice is INGRESS or EGRESS. In this specific scenario, the cognitive loop manages 16 concurrent devices. The SMPS identified 8 network interfaces to mitigate a single malicious flow. However, since the UE was sending two concurrent flows—one malicious and one legitimate—the cognitive loop’s management capacity effectively doubled.

Interface	Hostname	FlowId	DevId	sense
eth3	EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1	93698FF5	21A00354	EGRESS
eth0	EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1	7D437342	23A9F542	EGRESS
eth7	EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1	BE43457C	6EBB45FB	INGRESS
eth5	EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1	4B14E8CA	87AEF71A	INGRESS
eth6	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	9B3C9F0A	B36282BF	EGRESS
eth0	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	4899E2CD	CA96817C	INGRESS
eth3	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	491CD2AC	DF6053F9	INGRESS
eth7	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	7A57B464	EF54F629	EGRESS

Figure 21: End-to-End 5G/6G path calculated by the SMPS where the network slice is applied as mitigation action against DDoS attacks.

Figure 22 showcases the GUI tool developed by UWS for monitoring and analysing experiment results. The GUI displays network traffic for legitimate (top) and malicious (bottom) 5G flows from infected devices. The screenshot captures the mitigation moment, showing reduced malicious traffic in the Transport and Core segments, while the attack persists near the source. Legitimate traffic continues uninterrupted.

Figure 22: Validation GUI developed by UWS to show the bandwidth consumed by the infected UE and the mitigation response by the legitimate (top) and malicious (bottom) traffic.

Preliminary results include:

- Network slice limiting attack traffic to 1 Kbps (from 250 Mbps).
- Slice applied within <50 seconds of detection by NSFM.
- Automatic E2E data plane slice deployment.
- Normal TCP traffic flow maintained during mitigation.

The methodology used to calculate the different KPIs in those tests is described as follows. Moreover, the measured KPIs are shown in Table 13 below:

- KPI-9: The number of End-to-End network slices supported by the UWS-NSP has been validated at 2,048, as detailed in Section 6.1.4 of D3.2 [21] of the RIGOUROUS project, published by M18.
- KPI-10: The SMPS identified 8 network interfaces to mitigate a single malicious flow. However, since the User Equipment (UE) was transmitting two concurrent flows—one malicious and one legitimate—the cognitive loop’s management capacity effectively doubled. The number of devices is calculated based on the End-to-End path facilitated by the TIA component.

- KPI-20: For the mitigation time, we have considered adding the mean time needed for the Security Orchestrator to process the MSPL (including all related processes, such as conflict detection and policy translation) and the enforcement in the correspondent enabler.
- KPI-22: This KPI measures the total time the SOAR loop takes to create a single network slice. The time is calculated by summing the execution times of all components involved in the cognitive loop. Table 14 presents the individual execution times for up to five runs, expressed in seconds, along with the total calculated time.

Table 13: Measured KPIs for test case 3.

KPI #	Measured Value	Target Value
KPI-09	= 2048	>= 2048
KPI-10	16	> 1000
KPI-20	20.1304 sec	<240 seconds
KPI-22	36.0826	< 60 seconds

Table 14: Execution times of the SOAR loop components.

Run	NSFM	SMPS	SO	SM+NSP	Total
1	0.038	15.492	11.622	4.854	32.006
2	0.043	15.841	11.988	4.487	32.359
3	0.053	16.385	17.784	4.543	38.765
4	0.032	15.843	18.835	4.649	39.359
5	0.036	16	17.983	3.857	37.9
Mean	0.0404	15.9122	15.6524	4.478	36.0826

The complete execution time of the SOAR loop components will be compared with future prototypes to demonstrate advances in development and continuous performance improvements.

4.3.3. Test Cases 7

4.3.3.1. Description

Test Case 7 enriches the RIGOUROUS framework with the test setup for the identification and mitigation of malicious attackers or actors external to the network based on their activities reflected on the control plane of a telco network. This scenario depicts an external attacker (in this case registered UE) which performs DOS attack on the network by leveraging their capability to recursively register to the network as in TS23.502 Clause 4.2.2 [22]. This potentially disrupts the control plane functions due to the increased load on them as shown in D3.2 [23]. This test case involves multiple assets of the RIGOUROUS framework working together to demonstrate the identification and mitigation of such adversaries as follows:

- The TESP (R08) serves as identification in alignment of Prometheus (for monitoring) and Alert Manager (for generating alerts).

- The AI-driven Decision Engine (R16) serves as the decision maker for remediation action.
- The Security Orchestrator (R07) for performing the mitigation.

The Trust Evaluation and Scoring Framework (TESF - R08) identifies such anomalous behaviours by analysing alerts and logs from the involved network functions. It assigns trust scores to UEs based on the severity of their actions. When a UE’s trust score falls below a predefined threshold, the TESF alerts the AI-driven decision engine (AID - R16). The AID evaluates the situation and formulates an action policy, which it communicates to the Security Orchestrator (SO - R07). The SO enforces mitigation actions, such as dropping packets from the attacking UE to the AMF, effectively neutralizing the threat and restoring network stability.

Attack Strategy and Setup: As illustrated in Figure 23, we simulate the RAN-UE part using UERANSIM where a malicious UE was deployed with fixed IP addresses and 1 gNb connected to the AMF in the core network. The malicious UE, which is already stored in the subscriber database, performs a recursive registration procedure after its initial registration is completed. The attack is implemented using a bash script where the UE registration command is called followed by a sleep command of 2 sec and lastly terminating the process. This is done for 150 times, and the entire process takes about 425 seconds on average and the number of requests per second on the *lo* interface (the interface between AMF and UE) is 45 on average. This test case highlights the robustness of trust score-based detection and response mechanisms in securing network operations against control plane attacks.

Figure 23: Topology of test case 7 on UERANSIM testbed.

4.3.3.2. KPIs

The KPIs that will be measured within this test case are listed in the following Table 15:

Table 15: List of KPIs for test case 7.

KPI #	Description
KPI-20	Decrease mitigation time by 50% compared to SOTA.
KPI-21	Improve decision-making on threat mitigation by 45% compared to.

4.3.3.3. Results

The components involved in test case 7 have the following responsibilities:

1. The TESH (R08), triggered by the Prometheus and alert manager, analyses the logs of the Network function in the core network and produces trust scores based on the severity of the attack. When the trust score is below a threshold (here, we have considered 95), it sends a STIX message to the AID(R16) to enable mitigation action.
2. The AID, upon receiving such triggers, parses the STIX data and sends an MSPL policy to the Security Orchestrator through REST.
3. The Security Orchestrator(R07) deploys a Linux kernel-based firewall(iptables) from the data received from the MSPL policy and hence mitigates the attack that could potentially block the linkup of the gNb.

Figure 24 demonstrates the reaction of the TESH on receiving alerts from the alert manager and after analysis of the core network functions logs.

```
* Serving Flask app 'server_testf'
* Debug mode: on
WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment. Use a production WSGI server instead.
* Running on all addresses (:)
* Running on http://:::5004
* Running on http://:::5004
Press CTRL+C to quit
* Restarting with stat
* Debugger is active!
* Debugger PIN: 576-805-253
JSON file received and processed.
9997000000000001
127.0.0.1 127.0.0.5 9997000000000001
Updated IMSI 9997000000000001: Trust Score=100, IP=127.0.0.1, Alert Location=127.0.0.5
9997000000000001
127.0.0.1 127.0.0.5 9997000000000001
Updated IMSI 9997000000000001: Trust Score=95, IP=127.0.0.1, Alert Location=127.0.0.5
{"type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--b1722174-a688-488b-999b-6d2079c5b380", "objects": [{"type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--93fa51d8-5ccf-4db1-aae2-aa6ec53ec53d", "created": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.418732Z", "modified": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.418732Z", "error_type": "re-registration", "imsi": "9997000000000001", "ip": "127.0.0.1", "trust_score": 95}, {"type": "networkentity", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "networkentity--87ecd63-4f7d-497b-b538-e745830e76d", "created": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.419402Z", "modified": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.419402Z", "name": "anf", "ip": "127.0.0.1"}, {"type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--258f117b-d381-491d-9158-966585f5ab57", "created": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.419602Z", "modified": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.419602Z", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "anomalies--93fa51d8-5ccf-4db1-aae2-aa6ec53ec53d", "target_ref": "networkentity--87ecd63-4f7d-497b-b538-e745830e76d"}]}
Sending Alert for IMSI: 9997000000000001
9997000000000001
JSON file received and processed.
9997000000000001
JSON file received and processed.
9997000000000001
```

Figure 24: TESH-initiated attack identification and trust score evaluation.

Figure 24 shows how the AID analyses the STIX data through the Kafka broker, along with the details of the attacker, such as IMSI, IP, and end points. Figure 26 represents the behaviour of the Security Orchestrator when receiving a decision on actions to be taken to mitigate the attack.

```
decision-engine-1 | INFO: main: {"type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--b1722174-a688-488b-999b-6d2079c5b380", "objects": [{"type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--93fa51d8-5ccf-4db1-aae2-aa6ec53ec53d", "created": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.418732Z", "modified": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.418732Z", "error_type": "re-registration", "imsi": "9997000000000001", "ip": "127.0.0.1", "trust_score": 95}, {"type": "networkentity", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "networkentity--87ecd63-4f7d-497b-b538-e745830e76d", "created": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.419402Z", "modified": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.419402Z", "name": "anf", "ip": "127.0.0.1"}, {"type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--258f117b-d381-491d-9158-966585f5ab57", "created": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.419602Z", "modified": "2025-01-15T04:49:44.419602Z", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "anomalies--93fa51d8-5ccf-4db1-aae2-aa6ec53ec53d", "target_ref": "networkentity--87ecd63-4f7d-497b-b538-e745830e76d"}]}
```

Figure 25: AID logs on receiving alert from TESH in STIX format.

```

security-orchestrator-1 2025-01-15 05:49:44,550 INFO MSPL_OP Received
security-orchestrator-1 2025-01-15 05:49:44,564 INFO <?xml version="1.0" ?>
security-orchestrator-1 <ns1:ITResourceOrchestration id="mspl_5b6fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:ns1="http://modelisoftware/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-b66a854051a/ITResource_xsd">
security-orchestrator-1   <ns1:ITResource id="mspl_9e5db0bfaf544ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="mspl_5b6fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9">
security-orchestrator-1     <ns1:configuration xsi:type="ns1:RuleSetConfiguration">
security-orchestrator-1       <ns1:capability>
security-orchestrator-1         <ns1:Name>Firewall</ns1:Name>
security-orchestrator-1       </ns1:capability>
security-orchestrator-1     <ns1:configurationRule>
security-orchestrator-1       <ns1:configurationRuleAction xsi:type="ns1:FirewallRuleAction">
security-orchestrator-1         <ns1:firewallActionTypeX000P/>
security-orchestrator-1         <ns1:firewallActionType/>
security-orchestrator-1         </ns1:configurationRuleAction>
security-orchestrator-1       <ns1:configurationRuleCondition xsi:type="ns1:FirewallConfigurationCondition">
security-orchestrator-1         <ns1:isONF>false/</ns1:isONF>
security-orchestrator-1         <ns1:ruleParameters>
security-orchestrator-1           <ns1:isONF>false/</ns1:isONF>
security-orchestrator-1           <ns1:destinationAddress>127.0.0.5/</ns1:destinationAddress>
security-orchestrator-1           <ns1:actionDrop/>
security-orchestrator-1           <ns1:sourceAddress>127.0.0.1/</ns1:sourceAddress>
security-orchestrator-1           <ns1:name>ejemplol</ns1:name>
security-orchestrator-1         </ns1:ruleParameters>
security-orchestrator-1       </ns1:configurationRuleCondition>
security-orchestrator-1       <ns1:externalData xsi:type="ns1:Priority">
security-orchestrator-1         <ns1:value>60000/</ns1:value>
security-orchestrator-1       </ns1:externalData>
security-orchestrator-1       <ns1:ruleName/>
security-orchestrator-1       <ns1:isONF>false/</ns1:isONF>
security-orchestrator-1     </ns1:configurationRule>
security-orchestrator-1   </ns1:configuration>
security-orchestrator-1   <ns1:enablerCandidates>
security-orchestrator-1     <ns1:enabler>firewall</ns1:enabler>
security-orchestrator-1   </ns1:enablerCandidates>
security-orchestrator-1 </ns1:ITResource>
security-orchestrator-1 </ns1:ITResourceOrchestration>
  
```

Figure 26: Logs of the SO demonstrating the MSPL policy.

Figure 26 demonstrates the mitigation action end point and its response on deployment from the Security Orchestrator.

```

* Serving Flask app 'iptables.py'
* Debug mode: off
INFO:werkzeug:WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment. Use a production WSGI server instead.
* Running on all addresses (0.0.0.0)
* Running on http://127.0.0.1:11111
* Running on http://155.54.95.245:11111
INFO:werkzeug:Press CTRL+C to quit
[sudo] contraseña para rigourous-testenv: INFO:iptables:Rule iptables -A INPUT -s 127.0.0.1 -j DROP created
INFO:werkzeug:172.18.0.5 - - [15/Jan/2025 05:49:45] "POST /insert-rule HTTP/1.1" 200 -
  
```

Figure 27: Firewall Endpoint process on trigger from the SO.

Figure 27 validates the mitigation of the attack on the control plane by collecting packets from the interface between UE and AMF using tcpdump. This shows that using the RIGOUROUS framework to detect DOS attacks on control plane can be significantly mitigated within a short span of reaction time.

Figure 28: Diagram to demonstrate the difference of the impact of DoS attack on control plane with and without the proposed method.

In this test case, the KPIs are measured as follows:

- KPI-20: We measure the reaction time for mitigation from the moment the attack is initiated to the moment the Security Orchestrator deploys a firewall to drop the packets originating from the attacker, as shown in the formula below.

Mitigation Reaction Time = Time Instance of Attack Initiation - Time Instance of Firewall Deployment

- KPI-21: This KPI is measured as the time interval from when the attack is initiated until the AI-driven Decision Engine sends an MSPL policy to the Security Orchestrator, as shown in the formula below.

Mitigation Reaction Time = Time Instance of Attack Initiation - Time Instance of MSPL trigger

And below Table 16 shows the measured value of the KPIs during the test:

Table 16: Measured KPIs for test case 7.

KPI #	Measured Value	Target Value
KPI-20	70 sec	<240 seconds
KPI-21	50 sec	<60 seconds

4.3.4. Test Cases 8

4.3.4.1. Description

Test case 8 aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of the RIGOUROUS framework in detecting and mitigating HTTP-based application-layer DDoS attacks initiated by UEs against a vCDN Video-on-Demand service (deployed as NGINX web server in a cloud-native platform). The RIGOUROUS components involved in test case 8 are illustrated in Figure 9, presented in Section 3.3.3.2. The traffic to/from the web server is captured by the “tcpdump sidecar” attached to the UPF, then it is sent (in a pcap file) to the “Collector” module. The Collector module extracts the network flow features from the received pcap file and sends them to the “Detector” (i.e., asset R12) in a CSV file. The Detector analyses the CSV file using an MLP model and generates a binary classification, labelling network flows as "normal" or "ddos". An anomaly report in STIX format is published to the Kafka Broker (in R12-TRA-AID topic) for each network flow flagged as "ddos". The message is consumed by the AID (i.e., asset R16) to generate an MSPL for blocking the traffic between the malicious UEs and the web server. The MSPL is then sent to SO (i.e., asset R07), which triggers the invocation of the "add-rule" endpoint of the “PEAgent” deployed as a sidecar to the UPF. The call of the "add-rule" endpoint allows the enforcement of DROP rules in the UPF’s iptables, blocking the traffic between the malicious UE and the web server.

Both low-rate and high-rate HTTP-based DDoS attacks were tested using Goloris [17] and DoS-Tool [14] tools, respectively. For each attack, the tests were repeated at least thrice, allowing consistent evaluation of KPIs considered for test case 8.

Figure 28 shows the topology of the test cases involved assets along with the sequence of the messages.

Figure 29: Topology of test case 8.

4.3.4.2. KPIs

The KPIs that will be measured within this test case are shown in the below Table 17:

Table 17: List of KPIs for test case 8.

KPI #	Description
KPI-13	Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%
KPI-15	Ability to detect 2 unknown/unexpected scenarios and >4 types of anomalies
KPI-16	Number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10
KPI-22	Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480mn, RIGOUROUS: < 1mn)

KPI-13 is measured using the common Recall (aka Sensitivity) metric, given by the formula in Equation 3:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

Where TP (True Positive) represents the number of anomalies that are correctly detected, and FN (False Negative) denotes the number of anomalies that are falsely detected as normal samples.

KPI-22 is measured in terms of Mean-Time-to-Detection (MTTD) and Mean-Time-to-Mitigation (MTTM). MTTD represents the elapsed time between the onset of an attack and its successful detection (by the “Detector” module in our case). The MTTM is the time elapsed between the

starting of an attack and its mitigation (i.e., enforcement of the DROP rules in the UPF's iptables in our case).

4.3.4.3. Results

Table 18 presents screenshots of a test scenario related to a low-rate HTTP-based DDoS attack, showing the different stages of the implemented closed loop, from network traffic collection to mitigation.

Table 18: Stages of test case 8 for low-rate HTTP-based DDoS attack scenario.

<p>UE launches attack</p>	<pre> root@ueransim-gnb-ues-75f7648974-fx9qx:/tools/goloris# ./goloris -testDuration 1m -victimUrl http:// [REDACTED]:30666/DigitalOcean.mp4 -localInterface "10.45.0.8" 2024/12/16 13:09:55 Execution started at: 2024-12-16T13:09:55Z contentLength=1000000 dialWorkersCount=10 goMaxProcs=4 hostHeader= localInterface=10.45.0.8 rampUpInterval=1s sleepInterval=10s testDuration=1m0s victimUrl=http://[REDACTED]:30666/DigitalOcean.mp4 </pre> <p style="text-align: right;">UE</p>
<p>Traffic from to/from the web server is collected and uploaded to Collector</p>	<pre> chafikabenzaid -- root@open5gs-upf-5d4cc9dfcb-4g469:/capture -- 99x12 102 packets received by filter 0 packets dropped by kernel Uploading pcap files to Collector service... {"filename":"traffic.pcap"}Capturing traffic... tcpdump: listening on ogstun, link-type RAW (Raw IP), snapshot length 262144 bytes 100 packets captured 145 packets received by filter 0 packets dropped by kernel Uploading pcap files to Collector service... {"filename":"traffic.pcap"}Capturing traffic... tcpdump: listening on ogstun, link-type RAW (Raw IP), snapshot length 262144 bytes </pre> <p style="text-align: right;">Tcpdump Sidecar</p>
<p>Network flow features are extracted and uploaded to Detector</p>	<pre> INFO: 172.16.104.128:56211 - "POST /uploadfile/ HTTP/1.1" 200 OK INFO:collector:Features extraction phase started INFO:collector:Features extraction phase finished: 1.266012191772461 INFO: 172.16.104.128:13830 - "POST /uploadfile/ HTTP/1.1" 200 OK INFO:collector:Features extraction phase started INFO:collector:Features extraction phase finished: 1.2397844791412354 </pre> <p style="text-align: right;">Collector</p>
<p>Attack is detected and anomaly reports are published to Kafka broker</p>	<pre> chafikabenzaid -- ubuntu@k8s-master: ~ -- 91x12 2024-12-16 13:10:07 - Detector - INFO - Prediction phase finished. 2024-12-16 13:10:07 - Detector - INFO - ==== Normal traffic. INFO: 172.16.104.128:20802 - "POST /mlp/predict/ HTTP/1.1" 200 OK 2024-12-16 13:10:10 - Detector - INFO - Preprocessing phase started... 2024-12-16 13:10:10 - Detector - INFO - Preprocessing phase finished. 2024-12-16 13:10:10 - Detector - INFO - Prediction phase started... 1/1 [=====] - 0s 36ms/step 2024-12-16 13:10:10 - Detector - INFO - Prediction phase finished. 2024-12-16 13:10:10 - Detector - INFO - ==== Malicious traffic. 2024-12-16 13:10:10 - Detector - INFO - Message sent to topic 'R12-AID-TRA' with key 'b'RIG OUROUS-key'' </pre> <p style="text-align: right;">Detector</p>

Table 19 summarises the achieved KPI values for low- and high-rate HTTP-based DDoS attack scenarios.

Table 19: KPIs values achieved by test case 8.

KPI #		Low-rate HTTP-based DDoS attack	High-rate HTTP-based DDoS attack	Target Value
KPI-13		95%	100%	>95%
KPI-15		2 types of anomalies are detected. Specifically, anomalies related to low-rate and high-rate HTTP-based DDoS attacks.		>4
KPI-16		2 cyber-attacks are detected using a DL model.		>10
KPI-22	MTTD	15s	2s	<1mn
	MTTM	16.33s	3.5s	

The results depicted in Table 19 confirm the achievement of the measured KPIs. They show the contribution of KPI-15 and KPI-16 by supporting the detection of two kinds of attacks. Furthermore, the results demonstrate a high accuracy ($\geq 95\%$) in detecting HTTP-based DDoS attacks. However, detecting high-rate HTTP-based DDoS attacks is more effective than low-rate HTTP-based DDoS attacks. This can be attributed to the stealthy nature of low-rate HTTP-based DDoS attack, which consists of establishing multiple HTTP connections with the web server by sending partial HTTP requests very slowly. As a result, the first network flows generated by the attack are detected as usual, increasing the MTTD.

4.3.5. Test Cases 9

4.3.5.1. Description

In test case 9, two different kinds of attacks, namely a DDoS through a TCP SYN messages flood and a dictionary-based brute-force attack against an HTTP service, are launched in the UMU 5G testbed. The UMU 5 G Monitoring Sensor and UMU 5 G Flow Processor were used to monitor traffic and extract flow features for both the FL-based models training process and the real-time inference/detection.

In the first phase, benign traffic was generated, simulating several types of normal user behaviours (regular HTTP activity, normal SSH activity, etc.). This traffic was collected in real time by the UMU 5G Monitoring Sensor. The UMU 5G flow processor calculated flow features, which were fed to the previously deployed FL agents for training our model for anomaly detection, the Deep Autoencoder. Then, after this first phase, the two kinds of attacks previously enumerated were launched using attacker and victim machines in the testbed. For the first attack (TCP SYN DoS), the tool hping3 was used, while for the second attack (HTTP Dictionary), the open-source BruteforceHTTP [19] was used. That traffic was collected and used, in part, to train our attack classification model, i.e., the multi-class classification MLP, and in part, to test the autoencoder after the FL training and adjust the detection threshold.

Once the training of both models was completed, we have launched again both attacks using the same procedure. Now, both detection modules (anomaly detection and attack classification, part of UMU's R12 asset) were performed jointly to detect, classify and alert the flows related to the attacks using the STIXv2-based alerting format. These alerts were published in the R12-AID-TRA topic enabled for this purpose in the Kafka broker deployed in ONE's testbed, so the AID component will be able to consume this information in real-time to proceed with the mitigation process.

For this test case, a dummy AID component was used to forward a predefined mitigation action to the UMU's Security Orchestrator (R07), which will close the loop by applying the right countermeasure to stop the attacks.

In Figure 29, the topology of the test case with the attack detection (not training) flow can be found from the attack launch and traffic monitoring (steps 1 and 2), flow features calculation (steps 3 and 4), anomaly detection, attack classification and alerting (steps 5, 6 and 7), decision making (steps 8 and 9) and enforcement of mitigation action (step 10).

Figure 30: Topology of test case 9.

4.3.5.2. KPIs

The KPIs that will be measured within this test case are shown in the below Table 20:

Table 20: List of KPIs for test case 9.

KPI #	Description
KPI-13	Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%
KPI-14	Time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds (<1s)
KPI-15	Ability to detect 2 unknown/unexpected scenarios and >4 types of anomalies
KPI-17	Crypto-Privacy algorithms supported for privacy-preserving CTI sharing and FL sharing > 5

4.3.5.3. Results

Table 21 shows the description of the steps of the experiment carried out and a screenshot of the logs generated during the process.

Table 21: Stages of test case 9 for TCP SYN DoS and HTTP dictionary Druteforce attacks.

FL Agent receives training flows in real-time	<pre>[2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Flow successfully stored [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - GENERAL: New flow for training has been received [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding and storing flow... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Flow successfully stored [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - GENERAL: New flow for training has been received [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding and storing flow... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Flow successfully stored [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - GENERAL: New flow for training has been received [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding and storing flow... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Flow successfully stored [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - GENERAL: New flow for training has been received [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding and storing flow... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Flow successfully stored [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - GENERAL: New flow for training has been received [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding and storing flow... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Flow successfully stored</pre>
FL Agent has received enough flows to start training	<pre>[2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Flow successfully stored [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - GENERAL: New flow for training has been received [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding and storing flow... [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Flow successfully stored [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - GENERAL: There is enough data to start training [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - GENERAL: Starting Federated Learning process [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Creating training dataframe from stored flows... [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Training dataframe successfully created with shape (4001, 85) [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Retrieving training variables set from the FL Aggregator... [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Training variables set successfully retrieved and stored [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Remove discarded columns from the training dataframe... [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Discarded columns successfully removed from the training dataframe... [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Initiating FL Client with the processed training dataframe and additional parameters... [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Removing flow identifiers (IPs, ports)</pre>

<p>FL Agent creating the model (autoencoder) before training</p>	<pre>[2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - PROCESSING: Normalizing values [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: Column values have been normalized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance [2025-01-08 10:22:04 - FL Agent] INFO - RESULT: A Deep Autoencoder with the following architecture has been built and compiled: Model: "model" ----- Layer (type) Output Shape Param # ----- input_1 (InputLayer) [(None, 80)] 0 dense (Dense) (None, 40) 3240 dropout (Dropout) (None, 40) 0 dense_1 (Dense) (None, 20) 820 dense_2 (Dense) (None, 10) 210 dense_3 (Dense) (None, 20) 220 dropout_1 (Dropout) (None, 20) 0 dense_4 (Dense) (None, 40) 840 dense_5 (Dense) (None, 80) 3280 ----- Total params: 8610 (33.63 KB) Trainable params: 8610 (33.63 KB) Non-trainable params: 0 (0.00 Byte)</pre>
<p>FL Agent performing training throughout FL rounds (configured to 10)</p>	<pre>INFO : [RUN 0, ROUND] INFO : Received: evaluate message a73ddea0-cc03-47fc-9c70-bcf52aaf76e4 12/12 [=====] - 0s 2ms/step INFO : Sent reply INFO : [RUN 0, ROUND] INFO : Received: train message f8a78592-67c5-44bc-88f1-fd79a57c7b69 Epoch 1/2 1/1 [=====] - 0s 7ms/step - loss: 0.5907 Epoch 2/2 1/1 [=====] - 0s 4ms/step - loss: 0.7079 INFO : Sent reply INFO : [RUN 0, ROUND] INFO : Received: evaluate message 2ebd9f36-4e00-42b0-919b-cecb448cf2dc 12/12 [=====] - 0s 2ms/step INFO : Sent reply INFO : [RUN 0, ROUND] INFO : Received: train message 8a2bbafc-2a3a-4055-ae19-51a34c192a75 Epoch 1/2 1/1 [=====] - 0s 5ms/step - loss: 1.6760 Epoch 2/2</pre>
<p>FL Aggregator after FL training done (an auxiliary FL client is used to train along the previous one)</p>	<pre>INFO : aggregate_evaluate: received 2 results and 0 failures INFO : [ROUND 9] INFO : configure_fit: strategy sampled 2 clients (out of 2) INFO : aggregate_fit: received 2 results and 0 failures INFO : configure_evaluate: strategy sampled 2 clients (out of 2) INFO : aggregate_evaluate: received 2 results and 0 failures INFO : [ROUND 10] INFO : configure_fit: strategy sampled 2 clients (out of 2) INFO : aggregate_fit: received 2 results and 0 failures INFO : configure_evaluate: strategy sampled 2 clients (out of 2) INFO : aggregate_evaluate: received 2 results and 0 failures INFO : [SUMMARY] INFO : Run finished 10 round(s) in 12.97s INFO : History (loss, distributed): INFO : round 1: 0.8686327510463294 INFO : round 2: 0.8652080494549966 INFO : round 3: 0.862541987450533 INFO : round 4: 0.8604273357859222 INFO : round 5: 0.8587445058329131 INFO : round 6: 0.8573439476951477 INFO : round 7: 0.8561873549735675 INFO : round 8: 0.8552675062129574 INFO : round 9: 0.8544883517328129 INFO : round 10: 0.8538790523845662 INFO :</pre>

<p>Anomaly Detection Engine receiving the final model from the FL Agent</p>	<pre>[2025-01-08 09:44:26 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Waiting for the initial model and additional parameters... [2025-01-08 09:44:31 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Waiting for the initial model and additional parameters... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: New model (and its additional parameters) has been received [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Setting the new model as first detection model... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: New model has been set. Sending response... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Loading and preprocessing testing data (containing both normal and attack flows)... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Removing flow identifiers (IPs, ports) [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Replacing Infinite values for NaN values [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: 0 infinite values have been replaced by NaN [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Removing rows containing NaN (columns with number of NaN values >=1) [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: 0 rows containing NaN values have been removed [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Separating test dataset into benign and malign sub-datasets [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Original data has been successfully splitted based on label column values [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Removing label column [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Label column has been successfully removed [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Label column has been successfully removed [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Label encoding categorical values (if any) on both sub-datasets [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Label encoding successfully applied to columns: ['FlowType'] [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Label encoding successfully applied to columns: ['FlowType'] [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Normalizing values on both sub-datasets [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Column values have been normalized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Column values have been normalized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Testing model on testing data (containing both normal and attack flows)... [2025-01-08 09:44:36 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Calculating predictions/reconstructions of testing data samples 22/22 [=====] - 0s 1ms/step 22/22 [=====] - 0s 1ms/step [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Mean MSE (malign testset): 104.94 [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Mean MSE (benign testset): 8.25 [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Calculating metrics from results obtained [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: True Positives: 439 (64.18% of total) [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: True Negatives: 585 (85.53% of total) [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: False Positives: 99 (14.469999999999999% of total) [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: False Negatives: 245 (35.82% of total) [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Recall: 0.6418 [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Specificity: 0.8553 [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: F1 Score: 0.7185 [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Balanced accuracy: 0.7485 [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Cohen's Kappa: 0.4971 [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Creating Kafka consumer on specified broker/topic for receiving evaluation flows... [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Kafka consumer correctly created (now listening), on broker 10.208.11.72:39092 and topic named 'evaluation-flows-topic' [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Creating Kafka producer on specified broker/topic to publish abnormal flows metadata (alerts)... [2025-01-08 09:44:37 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Performing real-time anomaly detection against received evaluation flows...</pre>
<p>Attack Classification Engine performing its training in parallel to the other process previously described (and after, starts listening for incoming flows for classification)</p>	<pre>[2025-01-08 10:21:47 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Waiting for configuration... [2025-01-08 10:21:52 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Configuration request has been received [2025-01-08 10:21:52 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding parameters and configuring the engine... [2025-01-08 10:21:52 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Loading and preprocessing training/testing data (containing multiple classes) [2025-01-08 10:21:52 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - RESULT: Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine configured successfully. Starting... [2025-01-08 10:21:52 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Loading training data from path 'multiclass_df_umu_v12.csv' [2025-01-08 10:21:53 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - RESULT: Data has been loaded successfully [2025-01-08 10:21:53 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Replacing infinite values for NaN values [2025-01-08 10:21:53 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - RESULT: 0 infinite values have been replaced by NaN [2025-01-08 10:21:53 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Removing high null samples (percentage exceeding threshold) [2025-01-08 10:21:53 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - RESULT: 0 columns (0.0% of total) are dropped since their null values percentage excess 30.0% threshold [2025-01-08 10:21:53 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - RESULT: 0 columns (0.0% of total) are dropped since their null values percentage excess 30.0% threshold [2025-01-08 10:21:53 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Imputing NaN values in both categorical and numerical columns, if any [2025-01-08 10:21:54 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - RESULT: 0 NaN values on numerical columns, and 0 in categorical columns have been imputed [2025-01-08 10:21:54 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Removing atypical values (higher than 7 times the STD) [2025-01-08 10:21:54 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Label encoding categorical values (if any), except for label column [2025-01-08 10:21:54 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - RESULT: Label encoding successfully applied to columns: ['FlowType', 'Label'] [2025-01-08 10:21:54 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Normalizing values [2025-01-08 10:21:55 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - RESULT: Column values have been normalized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance [2025-01-08 10:21:55 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Splitting data into train and test sets [2025-01-08 10:21:55 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Creating the multi-class DNN for attack classification [2025-01-08 10:21:55 - Real-time AI-based Attack Classification Engine] INFO - GENERAL: Training the model on test data 1854/1854 [=====] - 4s 2ms/step - loss: 0.0146 - accuracy: 0.9994</pre>

<p>Anomaly Detection Engine receiving and evaluating flows in real-time (attack flows corresponding to TCP SYN DoS and HTTP Dictionary attacks)</p>	<pre> 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: New flow received for evaluation 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding flow information... 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Flow information successfully decoded 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - TIME: Decoding the flow received took 0.212 milliseconds. 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Label encoding was not applied since no category columns were found 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Normalizing values on current flow using existing scaler 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Column values have been normalized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - TIME: Preprocessing the flow received took 6.79 milliseconds. 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Predicting current flow against trained model and checking threshold 1/1 [=====] - 0s 19ms/step 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - TIME: Predicting the flow received took 64.108 milliseconds. 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - TIME: Evaluating (whole process) the flow received took 71.291 milliseconds. Flows processed: 86 Flows detected as attacks: 80 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - GENERAL: New flow received for evaluation 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Decoding flow information... 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Flow information successfully decoded 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - TIME: Decoding the flow received took 0.293688000000000000000000000004 milliseconds. 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Label encoding was not applied since no category columns were found 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Normalizing values on current flow using existing scaler 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Column values have been normalized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - TIME: Preprocessing the flow received took 6.137000000000000000000000000005 milliseconds. 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - PROCESSING: Predicting current flow against trained model and checking threshold 2/1 [=====] - 0s 19ms/step 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - TIME: Predicting the flow received took 61.119 milliseconds. 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - TIME: Evaluating (whole process) the flow received took 67.7190000000000000000000000001 milliseconds. 2025-01-09 12:09:33 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - DETECTION: Anomalous flow detected (6.5722 >= 2.576). { "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--b21bd2f7-f22c-4324-aa9b-9af4821d2aaf", "testbed": "UMU", "objects": [{ "type": "anomaly", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomaly--f6f856f-4de9-4d0b-bfa4-ec5788f8be12", "created": "2025-01-09T12:09:34", "modified": "2025-01-09T12:09:34", "value": 1.0, "value_type": "confidence", "flow_id": 996, "source_ip": 0, "source_port": 57494, "destination_ip": 0, "destination_port": 80, "flow_data": [] }] } </pre>
<p>Anomaly Detection Engine finishes processing all the incoming flows</p>	<pre> "TcpWinWindowSizeDL", "TcpAvgWindowSizeUL", "TcpAvgWindowSizeDL", "TcpNumPacketsFinUL", "TcpNumPacketsFinDL", "TcpNumPacketsSynUL", "TcpNumPacketsSynDL", "TcpNumPacketsRstUL", "TcpNumPacketsRstDL", "TcpNumPacketsPshUL", "TcpNumPacketsPshDL", "TcpNumPacketsAckUL", "TcpNumPacketsAckDL", "TcpNumPacketsUrgUL", "TcpNumPacketsUrgDL"], "multi_class_accuracy": 99.99606593493057, "framework": "tensorflow", "version": "2.15.0", "collection_tool": "umu-5g-flow-processor", "collection_tool_version": "v1.0", "training_timestamp": 1736340567000 }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--80ffec6d-5df5-48e7-a8dd-9da0f9690aab", "created": "2025-01-08T12:55:40", "modified": "2025-01-08T12:55:40", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "model--5146bccf-2024-4101-8afb-f4c92da06fda", "target_ref": "anomaly--dedf2029-b1fb-48fa-9eae-663f422de909" }] } 2025-01-08 12:55:40 - Real-time AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine] INFO - RESULT: Abnormal flow metadata successfully published on alerts topic CFFlows processed: 2000 Flows detected as attacks: 1847 </pre>

From the previous figures, it can be seen that a total of 2000 flows (1000 corresponding to each kind of attack) have been launched and monitored, the corresponding flows and their statistics have been generated and sent to the Anomaly Detection Engine, and a total of 1847 have been detected as anomalies (out of 2000, giving a 92.35% of accuracy on anomaly detection), classified by the Attack Classification Engine into one of the two attack classes and alerted to the output Kafka topic following the agreed STIXv2-based data format. Within the FL process, Gaussian noise has been added to the weights exchanged with the aggregator in each model update to achieve a differentially private process and to contribute to the KPI 17. Finally, in the logs we can see that the total time spent in decoding, pre-processing and evaluating the flow, for the flow shown in the

figures, is around 67 milliseconds. The mean spent for the 2000 assessed flows is 61.5 milliseconds, which shows the detection process achieves KPI-15.

Table 22 shows the achieved KPIs (expected values vs. results obtained after the experimentation). As can be seen, KPI-13 is nearing completion, KPI-15 is achieved with a significant margin, and KPI-17 is partially addressed. However, more privacy-preserving techniques must be added, which will be addressed in the next prototype.

Table 22: KPI values achieved by test case 9.

<i>KPI #</i>	<i>Measured Value</i>	<i>Target Value</i>
KPI-13	92.35%	>95%
KPI-14	61.5 ms	<1s
KPI-15	2 attacks	4 attacks/types of anomalies and 2 unknown scenarios
KPI-17	1	5

5 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D5.2, Platform Prototype Integration and In-Lab Testing marks a pivotal step in the RIGOUROUS project, successfully validating core assets' integration and functionality within a controlled environment. This deliverable reports the results from the first round of tests, encompassing six test cases designed to evaluate the framework's ability to handle a variety of cybersecurity threats. These tests, conducted across multiple environments and testbeds, provided valuable insights into the system's operational and performance capabilities while identifying areas for further improvement.

Three key conclusions emerge from this phase of testing, offering critical feedback for subsequent technical work packages, particularly WP3 and WP4:

1. Operational Validation:

The results confirmed that the information flow between components within the RIGOUROUS architecture performed as expected. Interfaces between assets functioned seamlessly, facilitating the smooth transmission and processing of data during all test cases. This validates the integration and coordination of core components, demonstrating the architecture's ability to handle anomalies and threats effectively.

2. Strong Performance Achievements:

- The tests exhibited robust system performance in anomaly detection and mitigation, with several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) achieving or exceeding their targets:
 - KPI-20 (end-to-end mitigation reaction time) recorded exceptional results, such as 3.5 seconds in Test Cases 1 and 2 and approximately 20 seconds in Test Case 3.
 - KPI-21 (decision-making time for mitigation actions) demonstrated highly efficient processing times, with 2.5 seconds recorded in Test Cases 1 and 2, and 50 seconds in Test Case 7. This indicates minimal delays across system functionalities.
 - KPI-22 (mean time to mitigate across the cognitive loop) consistently achieved times under 60 seconds, meeting the target threshold.

3. Areas for Improvement:

While operational and performance results were strong, some challenges remain in achieving the desired system accuracy.

- Anomaly detection accuracy fell short of the 95% target, with KPI-13 reporting approximately 70%. This highlights the need for further optimisation in detection algorithms.
- Despite a significant reduction in false alarms (KPI-12 recorded more than a 45% reduction), further improvements in accuracy are needed to refine the system's effectiveness. These shortcomings will be addressed by leveraging these findings to guide refinements in WP3 and WP4, ensuring that the system evolves to meet its ambitious performance goals.

This deliverable confirms the maturity and potential of the RIGOUROUS toolkit. Prototype 1 demonstrated substantial progress across several metrics, providing a solid foundation for the next phase of development. The outcomes of this testing phase will be instrumental in refining and integrating the complete set of toolkit assets in Prototype 2. The RIGOUROUS project is on track to deliver a comprehensive, reliable, and high-performing cybersecurity solution for next-generation

5G/6G networks by addressing the identified areas for improvement and continuing iterative enhancements.

ANNEX A – INTERFACE DEFINITION

OT-WEB_UI

Field	Description
Interface code	OT-WEB_UI
Status	design
Component #1	Onboarding Tools
Component #2	Enhanced Human-Centric WEB UI
Direction	#2 to #1
Description	Enforce policies received from the Security Orchestrator
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	TBD
Operation	Multiple
Request/Data Schema	Is dependent on the endpoint
Request/Data Example	TBD
Response Schema	The usual response is a REST 200 - OK.
Response Example	NA
Impact on #Component 1	The Onboarding Tools provides all necessary endpoints for the WEB_UI, effectively functioning as the backend
Impact on #Component 2	The WEB_UI interfaces with the Onboarding Tools for functionality, specifically to onboard NFV descriptors with the enhanced security and privacy capabilities

TESF-AID

Field	Description
Interface code	TESF-AID
Status	Implemented
Component #1	TESF
Component #2	Decision Engine
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	The TESF will send the trust score, ip of a network entity and impacted ip to the Decision Engine in events where the trust score of a network is below a given threshold
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON (STIX2)
Endpoint	Kafka topic TESF-AID
Operation	Publish
Request/Data Schema	<pre>{ "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--d8167b99-c9b8-4963-8677-b9e6181a76dd", "objects": [{ "type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--57471174-8854-496a-b317-9c012e2f7713", "created": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436155+00:00", "modified": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436155+00:00", "error_type": "re-registration", "imsi": "999170000000001", "ip": "192.168.100.2", "trust_score": 45, "revoked": false }], }</pre>

	<pre>{ "type": "networkentity", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "networkentity--56b37ced-e0cb-4f14-803a-e52714e419c5", "created": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436475+00:00", "modified": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436475+00:00", "name": "amf", "ip": "172.22.0.10:9091", "revoked": false }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--f8c0c9e0-7311-480b-9498-839e3a4c7418", "created": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436631+00:00", "modified": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436631+00:00", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "anomalies--57471174-8854-496a-b317-9c012e2f7713", "target_ref": "networkentity--56b37ced-e0cb-4f14-803a-e52714e419c5", "revoked": false }]</pre>
Request/Data Example	Given in Request Schema
Response Schema	N.A
Response Example	N.A
Impact on #Component 1	When the trust score threshold of network entity like UE is below a certain threshold(customizable), the TESH will publish the given data to a specific kafka topic.

Impact on #Component 2	The decision engine subscribed to the same kafka topic will take some decision based on the trust score and other related features (which may result in a threat mitigation).
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SO-TESF

Field	Description
Interface code	SO-TESF
Status	development
Component #1	TESF
Component #2	Security Orchestrator
Direction	#2 to #1
Description	Request for Trust score from the any management domain entities to the TESF for network entities (for example IMSI)
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON (STIX2)
Endpoint	Endpoint - :8765/target
Operation	GET
Request/Data Schema	{ "target_id": "IMSI or IP" }
Request/Data Example	{ "target_id": "999170000000001" } "GET /target?value=999170000000001HTTP/1.1"
Response Schema	{ "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--d8167b99-c9b8-4963-8677-b9e6181a76dd", "objects": [{ "type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--57471174-8854-496a-b317-9c012e2f7713", "created": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436155+00:00", "modified": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436155+00:00", }] }

	<pre>"error_type": "re-registration", "imsi": "999170000000001", "ip": "192.168.100.2", "trust_score": 0, "revoked": false }, { "type": "networkentity", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "networkentity--56b37ced-e0cb-4f14-803a-e52714e419c5", "created": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436475+00:00", "modified": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436475+00:00", "name": "amf", "ip": "172.22.0.10:9091", "revoked": false }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--f8c0c9e0-7311-480b-9498-839e3a4c7418", "created": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436631+00:00", "modified": "2024-11-11T13:42:25.436631+00:00", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "anomalies--57471174-8854-496a-b317-9c012e2f7713", "target_ref": "networkentity--56b37ced-e0cb-4f14-803a-e52714e419c5", "revoked": false }] }</pre>
Response Example	Given in Response Schema

Impact #Component 1	on	The SO will get the trust score and will act based on the defined policy for taking an proactive or reactive measures.
Impact #Component 2	on	The TESH will provide the trust score of the network entity.

SO-AID

Field	Description
Interface code	Unique identifier of the interface
Status	development
Component #1	Decision Engine
Component #2	Security Orchestrator
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	Generate specific configuration messages for devices to enforce policies from the Decision Engine
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	MSPL
Endpoint	:8002/meservice
Operation	POST
Request/Data Schema	Is dependant on the policy to enforce
Request/Data Example	<pre><?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omsp_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="omsp_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9"> <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>commandControl</Name> </capability> <configurationRule></pre>

	<pre> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="CommandControlRuleAction"> <commandControlActionType>CAMERA</commandControlActionType> </configurationRuleAction> <configurationCondition xsi:type="CommandControlConfigurationCondition "> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <cameraRuleParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <request>>true</request> <action>stoprecording</action> <macAddress>00:00:00:00:00</macAddress> <command_id>1234567890</command_id> </cameraRuleParameters> </configurationCondition> <externalData xsi:type="Priority"> <value>60000</value> </externalData> <Name>Rule0</Name> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> </configurationRule> <Name>Conf0</Name> </configuration> <enablerCandidates> <enabler>one_mobitrust</enabler> </enablerCandidates> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration> </pre> <p>(Example of a stop recording policy from the ONE Mobitrust use case)</p>
Response Schema	Is dependent on the implementation of the driver in charge of the MSPL processing, but the usual response is a REST 200 - OK.
Response Example	NA

Impact on #Component 1	The Decision Engine generates a MSPL policy to mitigate an anomaly detected in the system
Impact on #Component 2	The Security Orchestrator processes the MSPL policy received and generates a configuration message for the target device in order to enforce the policy

SO- Security agent

Field	Description
Interface code	Unique identifier of the interface
Status	development
Component #1	Security Orchestrator
Component #2	Security Agent
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	Enforcement of security policies from the Security Orchestrator to the Security Agents (that are connected to devices) through configuration messages
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	Dependant on the Security Agent, but in most cases JSON
Endpoint	Dependant on the Security Agent
Operation	Dependant on the Security Agent
Request/Data Schema	Dependant on the policy to enforce
Request/Data Example	<pre>{ "body": { "openc2": { "request": { "action": "stoprecording", "target": { "mac-addr": "00:00:00:00:00" } }, "command_id": "1234567890" } } }</pre> <p>(Example of a OpenC2 configuration message for the ONE Mobitrust use case)</p>

Response Schema	Dependant on the Security Agent implementation
Response Example	NA
Impact on #Component 1	The Security Orchestrator generates and sends specific configuration messages from MSPL policies for target Security Agent
Impact on #Component 2	The Security Agent receives configuration messages from the Security Orchestrator and enforces the new configuration in the corresponding device / element.

SO-SM

Field	Description
Interface code	SO-SM
Status	development
Component #1	Security Orchestrator
Component #2	Security Manager
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	The interface is based on communication between the security orchestrator and the Slice manager via an endpoint.
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	HTTP, REST
Format	XML
Endpoint	http://uws.fayos.org:18080/rest/rigorous/init
Operation	POST
Request/Data Schema	Is dependent on the policy to enforce
Request/Data Example	<pre><?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618- beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c- 8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9"> <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>Network_slicing</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="NetworkSlicingAction"> <NetworkSlicingActionType>CREATE</NetworkSlicingActionType> </configurationRuleAction></pre>

	<pre> <configurationCondition xsi:type="NetworkSlicingCondition"> <isCNF>false</isCNF> <qosCondition> <isCNF>false</isCNF> <priority>1</priority> <maxBandwidth>10000000</maxBandwidth> <minBandwidth>1000000</minBandwidth> </qosCondition> <networkSlicingConditionParameters> <isCNF>false</isCNF> <SliceName>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING22.sql</SliceName> <point> <isCNF>false</isCNF> <dpid>05DAB551</dpid> <dpid>05DAB551</dpid> </point> <SliceLocation>FE9B4176-14A9EFCC</SliceLocation> </networkSlicingConditionParameters> </configurationCondition> <Name>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</Name> <isCNF>false</isCNF> </configurationRule> <Name>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</Name> </configuration> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration> </pre>
Response Schema	The usual response is a REST 200 - OK.
Response Example	NA
Impact #Component 1	on The Security Orchestrator send configuration to configure services.
Impact #Component 2	on The Slicing Manager is able to be configured.

UWS-SM and UWS-NSP

Field	Description
Interface code	SM-NSP
Status	Validation
Component #1	Slice Manager
Component #2	Network Self-Protection
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	<p>The SM sends to the NSP an excerpt of one "technology-agnostic slice definition" JSON message which contains, among other, the following information:</p> <p>Host where the network slice will be instantiated ("deviceHostName")</p> <p>Network interface in the host where the slice will be attached ("iface")</p> <p>Slice enabler ("programmableTechnology")</p> <p>Interface status reported by RIA ("state","devicePortSpeed","currentTXQueues")</p> <p>QoS parameters of the slice ("minbandwidth","maxbandwidth","priority")</p> <p>Traffic sense of the slice. It could be uplink or downlink ("sense")</p> <p>Unique slice ID ("sliceName")</p> <p>Action timestamps</p>
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	AQMP
Format	JSON
Endpoint	Endpoint
Operation	Publish-subscribe
Request/Data Schema	Dependant on the action to be taken (e.g. create slice, attach flow to slice, etc)
Request/Data Example	<pre>"Resources": [{ "deviceHostName": "EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1", "iface": "eth0", "programmableTechnology":</pre>

	<pre>"UWS_NETWORK_SELF_PROTECTION", "queueDiscipline": "htb", "queueLength": "1000", "currentTxQueues": 1, "deviceResourceId": "FEAB99FD", "devicePortSpeed": "10000000000", "resourceId": "23A9F542", "state": "UP", "reportedTime": 1716458779392 }], "Intent": { "plannedTime": 1716458812793, "intentTargetResourceId": "23A9F542", "actionType": "INSERT", "actionName": "CONFIGURE_SLICE_DL", "sense": "EGRESS", "orderId": 1, "stepId": 1, "resourceId": "37DA525F", "reportedTime": 1716458812793, "minbandwidth": 10000, "maxbandwidth": 30000, "sliceName": "37DA525F" } }</pre>
Response Schema	None
Response Example	None
Impact on #Component 1	The SM sends a “technology-agnostic slice definition” JSON message to the NSP to enforce the mitigation action in the B5G data plane.
Impact on #Component 2	The NSP receives, in a particular order, the slice definitions as mitigation actions and enforces them in the B5G dataplane, thus mitigating the attack detected.

SM - SO

Field	Description
Interface code	SO-SM
Status	development
Component #1	Security Orchestrator
Component #2	Security Manager
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	The interface is based on communication between the security orchestrator and the Slice manager via an endpoint.
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	HTTP, REST
Format	XML
Endpoint	http://uws.fayos.org:18080/rest/rigorous/init
Operation	POST
Request/Data Schema	Is dependent on the policy to enforce
Request/Data Example	<pre><?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618- beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c- 8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="omsp1_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9"> <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>Network_slicing</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="NetworkSlicingAction"> <NetworkSlicingActionType>CREATE</NetworkSlicingActionType> </configurationRuleAction></pre>

	<pre> <configurationCondition xsi:type="NetworkSlicingCondition"> <isCNF>false</isCNF> <qosCondition> <isCNF>false</isCNF> <priority>1</priority> <maxBandwidth>10000000</maxBandwidth> <minBandwidth>1000000</minBandwidth> </qosCondition> <networkSlicingConditionParameters> <isCNF>false</isCNF> <SliceName>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING22.sql</SliceName> <point> <isCNF>false</isCNF> <dpid>05DAB551</dpid> <dpid>05DAB551</dpid> </point> <SliceLocation>FE9B4176-14A9EFCC</SliceLocation> </networkSlicingConditionParameters> </configurationCondition> <Name>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</Name> <isCNF>false</isCNF> </configurationRule> <Name>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</Name> </configuration> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration> </pre>
Response Schema	The usual response is a REST 200 - OK.
Response Example	NA
Impact #Component 1	on The Security Orchestrator send configuration to configure services.
Impact #Component 2	on The Slicing Manager can be configured.

NSFM-SMPS

Field	Description
Interface code	NSFM-SMPS
Status	validation
Component #1	Network Security Flow Monitoring
Component #2	Slice Mitigation Planner Service
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	The interface is a RabbitMQ topic where the NSFM will notify the alert regarding the malicious B5G flow detected with the specific and fine-grained metadata of the malicious flow with its nested B5G encapsulations.
Mode	Asynchronous
Standards/Protocols	AMQP
Format	JSON
Endpoint	endpoint (internal)
Operation	publish-subscribe
Request/Data Schema	<pre>{ "Resource": { "flowResourceId": Long, "parentResourceId": "String", "encapsulationLayer": Integer, "encapsulationID1": " String ", "encapsulationID2": " String ", "encapsulationType1": " String ", "encapsulationType2": " String ", "sense": " String ", "outMacSrc": " String ", "outMacDst": " String ", "srcIP": " String ", "dstIP": " String ", "outSrcIP": " String ", "outDstIP": " String ", } }</pre>

	<pre>"l4Proto": " String ", "tos": " String ", "srcPort": " String ", "dstPort": " String ", "l7Proto": " String ", "resourceAbstractionLayer": " String ", "resourceId": " String ", "resourceType": " String ", "state": " String ", "serviceInstanceResourceId": "String", "reportedTime": Long }, "Alert": { "alertType": " String ", "alertReasonId": " String ", "alertAssertionType": " String ", "alertImpact": Long, "alertTime": Long, "resourceId": " String ", "resourceType": " String ", "state": " String ", "serviceInstanceResourceId": " String ", "reportedTime": Long } }</pre>
Request/Data Example	<pre>{ "Resource": { "flowResourceId": "559238A1", "parentResourceId": "A0ADAEB6", "encapsulationLayer": 2, "encapsulationID1": "00000AF0",</pre>

	<pre>"encapsulationID2": "00000001", "encapsulationType1": "vxlan", "encapsulationType2": "gtp", "sense": "INGRESS", "outMacSrc": "40:00:00:02:00:01", "outMacDst": "40:00:00:02:00:02", "srcIP": "10101100000010001101111000000001", "dstIP": "10101100000010001101111011111110", "outSrcIP": "00001010000000100000000000000010", "outDstIP": "000010100000001000000000000000100", "l4Proto": "17", "tos": "0", "srcPort": "10000", "dstPort": "80", "l7Proto": "http", "resourceAbstractionLayer": "2", "resourceId": "CBB6599F", "resourceType": "FLOW_SAMPLE", "state": "ACTIVE", "serviceInstanceResourceId": "16168DAF", "reportedTime": 1668622718223 }, "Alert": { "alertType": "7", "alertReasonId": "10000002", "alertAssertionType": "NEGATIVE", "alertImpact": 2, "alertTime": 1668622717084, "resourceId": "58D7B372", "resourceType": "ALERT", "state": "FIRED", "serviceInstanceResourceId": "16168DAF",</pre>
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	<pre>"reportedTime": 1668622718233 } }</pre>
Response Schema	None
Response Example	None
Impact on #Component 1	The NSFMS triggers the alert with the B5G malicious flow metadata detected.
Impact on #Component 2	The SMPS consumes the alert and checks all the appearances of the detected malicious flows in the whole B5G network topology. Then it will send a set of plans to mitigate each of those network flows via the network Slice Manager to the Security Orchestrator (UMU).

TIA-SMPS

Field	Description
Interface code	TIA-SMPS
Status	Validation
Component #1	Topology Inventory Agent
Component #2	Slice Mitigation Planner Service
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	The interface is a RabbitMQ topic where the TIA will periodically notify the SMPS about the B5G network topology with respect to the network and host resources.
Mode	Asynchronous
Standards/Protocols	AMQP
Format	JSON
Endpoint	endpoint (internal)
Operation	publish-subscribe
Request/Data Schema	<pre>{ "devicePort": { "iface": "String", "devicePortType": "String", "deviceHostName": Integer, "mac": " String ", "ipv4": " String ", "ipv4Mask": " String ", "devicePortSpeed": " String ", "mtu": " Long ", "promiscuous": " Bool ", "state": " String " } }</pre>
Request/Data Example	<pre>{ "devicePort": { "iface": "eth1", "devicePortType": "LOGICAL",</pre>

	<pre>"deviceHostName": CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4, "mac": "40:00:00:01:00:06 ", "ipv4": " 10.1.0.17", "ipv4Mask": "16 ", "devicePortSpeed": " 10000000000 ", "mtu": " 1500 ", "promiscuous": " false", "state": "UP " }</pre>
Response Schema	None
Response Example	None
Impact on #Component 1	The TIA periodically notifies about the state of the host and network resources of the servers it is distributed.
Impact on #Component 2	The SMPS utilises TIA's information to correlate the information about the malicious flows detected and provide the End to End topology path where the network slice will be done as a mitigation action by the Slice Manager.

SMPS-SO

Field	Description
Interface code	SMPS-SO
Status	Validation
Component #1	Slice Mitigation Planner Service
Component #2	Security Orchestrator
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	The SMPS sends a set of 6 different plans to the Security Orchestrator with the specific rules (e.g. create network slice, attach flow to slice, etc). The SO will enable the system with the orchestration of the slices to be done in the B5G network in the correct order and locations in the network topology.
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	HTTP
Format	XML
Endpoint	e.g., api/endpoint
Operation	e.g., GET, POST, publish, subscribe
Request/Data Schema	Dependant on the specific rule (e.g. create network slice, attach flow to slice, etc)
Request/Data Example	<pre><?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns=http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd xmlns:xsi=http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance id="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation=http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd> <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9"> <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>Network_slicing</Name> </capability> <configurationRule></pre>

```
<configurationRuleAction
xsi:type='NetworkSlicingAction' >
  <NetworkSlicingActionType>CREATE</NetworkSlicingActionType>
</configurationRuleAction>
<configurationCondition xsi:type="NetworkSlicingCondition">
  <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
  <qosCondition>
    <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
    <priority>1</priority>
    <maxBandwidth>10000000</maxBandwidth>
    <minBandwidth>1000000</minBandwidth>
  </qosCondition>
  <networkSlicingConditionParameters>
    <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
    <SliceName>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</SliceName>
    <point>
      <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
      <dpid>05DAB551</dpid>
    </point>
  </networkSlicingConditionParameters>
</configurationCondition>
<Name>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</Name>
<isCNF>>false</isCNF>
</configurationRule>
<Name>FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql</Name>
</configuration>
</ITResource>
</ITResourceOrchestration>
```

Response Schema	None
Response Example	None
Impact on #Component 1	The SMPS creates the set of plans to mitigate the malicious flow with the E2E path correlated with the information provided by the TIA and NSFM.
Impact on #Component 2	The SO receives the SMPS plans and orchestrates the decisions to be taken in order to mitigate the threat in the B5G network.

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